

Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling:
Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science
for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action

D6.2 – IAM COMPACT CDE plan – Update 1

WP6 – Explaining – Policy
analysis, capacity development,
communication, dissemination,
exploitation.

28/02/2024

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is the first update of the IAM COMPACT Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) plan, which was developed and submitted at the early stages of the project. Its main purpose is to review the CDE strategy planned for the first 18 months of the project, and to report on the work carried out so far in the implementation of the project, hence informing involved partners on the success of their activities. This is done via a set of specific trackable targets and performance indicators, achieving which will ensure the realisation of the IAM COMPACT project's strategic objectives and long-term goals. To this end, this submission formalises the key mechanism to guide our future outreach effort and, as such, it serves as a reference framework for planning and implementing the project's communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities as well as evaluating their impact during the project's lifetime. In addition, it may serve as a practical guidebook to assist research teams and a diverse target audience in the field of integrated assessment modelling and climate policymaking to potentially identify best practices and new approaches to maximise their public outreach in a way that is both efficient and effective.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

A consolidated CDE plan, able to ensure high academic excellence and practical usability, is considered key in the project's effort to maximise the impact of its results and their use in policymaking towards supporting the Paris Agreement goals and NDC pledges. All corresponding CDE activities lie at the core of the project, as reflected in the "Explaining" pillar (policy analysis, capacity development, communication, dissemination, exploitation), aiming to establish a two-way science-policy/-society dialogue in a timely manner and via the best means available.

This document is the first update to the initial CDE plan, which was issued at the beginning of the project and detailed the strategy to be followed (D6.1). Its purpose is to describe and evaluate the actions undertaken so far for maximising the impact of IAM COMPACT and for supporting proactive engagement with different stakeholder groups, considering "why", "who", "what", "when", and "how" to engage. To fulfil these objectives, different means for communication and dissemination have been established alongside activities for meaningfully involving target audiences in knowledge co-creation with the goal to enhance the legitimacy of the scientific process and to improve the transparency and uptake of the produced scientific outcomes and modelling results.

Overall, the IAM COMPACT CDE activities are on track, following the initial plan laid out in the Grant Agreement and the first version of the CDE plan. The focus is placed on reiterating and strengthening the entire consortium's commitment to actively contributing to and boosting the impact and the exploitation potential of IAM COMPACT.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

IAM COMPACT supports the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, and the design of the next round of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries. It uses a diverse ensemble of models, tools, and insights from social and political sciences and operations research, integrating bodies of knowledge to co-create the research process and enhance transparency, robustness, and policy relevance. It explores the role of structural changes in major emitting sectors and of political, behaviour, and social aspects in mitigation, quantifies factors promoting or hindering climate neutrality, and accounts for extreme scenarios, to deliver a range of global and national pathways that are environmentally effective, viable, feasible, and desirable. In doing so, it fully accounts for COVID-19 impacts and recovery strategies and aligns climate action with broader sustainability goals, while developing technical capacity and promoting ownership in non-high-income countries.

NTUA – National Technical University of Athens	EL	
Aalto – Aalto Korkeakoulusaatio SR	FI	
AAU – Aalborg Universitet	DK	
BC3 – Asociacion BC3 Basque Centre for Climate Change – Klima Aldaketa Ikergai	ES	
Bruegel – Bruegel AISBL	BE	
CARTIF – Fundacion CARTIF	ES	
CICERO – Cicero Senter for Klimaforskning Stiftelse	NO	
E3M – E3-Modelling AE	EL	
KTH – Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan	SE	
POLIMI – Politecnico di Milano	IT	
UPRC – University of Piraeus Research Center	EL	
UVa – Universidad De Valladolid	ES	
WI – Wuppertal Institut fur Klima, Umwelt, Energie GGMBH	DE	
IIMA – Indian Institute of Management	IN	
THU – Tsinghua University	CN	
USMF – University System of Maryland	US	
AAiT – Addis Ababa University	ET	
KEI – International Civic Organisation Kyiv Economics Institute	UA	
RUSL – Raja Rata University of Sri Lanka	LK	
TUM – Technical University of Mombasa	KE	
UNIGE – Université de Genève	CH	
Imperial – Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine	UK	

Executive Summary

As much as communication remains a key requirement for any research project to raise awareness on and achieve visibility of the research outputs, IAM COMPACT also emphasises the importance of dissemination and exploitation as integral parts of the overall outreach strategy followed to increase impact over three overarching dimensions: scientific, societal, and economic. In other words, to ensure public engagement and social confidence in science and innovation, while making the potentially exploitable results useful in concrete contexts of action, even after the funded period of a project has ended. These issues may affect what can or cannot be done within the communication process and are likely to dictate the appropriate activities to be taken along the way.

In the IAM COMPACT project, the proposed Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) plan employs a variety of activities to facilitate an effective two-way engagement between the consortium and relevant stakeholder groups (policymakers, energy system and climate-economy modellers, industry representatives, NGOs, civil society, etc.), pursuing the purpose of fostering policy change in the field of integrated assessment modelling, based on its research findings. These activities range from a strong use of online communication channels, such as the website and social media, and a targeted scientific outreach, including scientific publications and participation in a number of conferences, to a set of more dynamic procedures to facilitate the co-creation of the research process. The latter revolves around two fundamental instruments of the project, the I²AM PARIS open-access data exchange modelling platform, and the Policy Response Mechanism (PRM), which inter alia helps to reach and engage a large body of actors within the scientific community, civil society, and the policy world.

This report is the first update to the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, aiming to inform on the progress towards achieving CDE goals, and further outlining updated—based on the lessons learnt—guidelines, strategies, and workflows for the consortium partners to continue following in their promotional activities and/or engage in mutual dialogue with different core stakeholders. This is achieved by critically evaluating the effectiveness of actions undertaken so far, and verifying, adapting, and refining our strategy and procedures accordingly to increase the visibility and usability of the project and ensure the mobilisation of a wide variety of our intended target audience. Special focus is placed on capturing new impact-effective opportunities, also considering actions towards the future exploitation of the main project achievements. The report constitutes a strategic deliverable of the IAM COMPACT project that falls under the scope of the “Explaining” pillar and will serve as a “living document” throughout the project, guiding the future CDE effort carried out by the consortium. A final update will follow at the end of the third year of the project (Month 36), including the final C&D outcomes, as well as outline exploitation objectives and details for the final EU conference as well as the IAM COMPACT partner-specific exploitation activities for all the different scientific outcomes produced.

Contents

EC Summary Requirements	ii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Objective and scope of the deliverable	1
1.2 Structure of the deliverable.....	2
2 The IAM COMPACT CDE plan	3
2.1 A brief overview of the CDE strategy	3
2.1.1 Messages (What/Why).....	4
2.1.2 Audience (Whom).....	6
2.1.3 Tools (How).....	9
2.1.4 Implementation agenda (When).....	10
2.2 Expected impact and outcomes.....	12
2.2.1 Measuring the expected outcomes and impact	12
2.2.2 Key performance indicators (KPIs).....	17
3 Management of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan	19
3.1 Phase 1: Communication strategy (M1-M36).....	20
3.1.1 Planned communication means	20
3.1.2 Implemented communication tools and activities.....	21
3.2 Phase 2: Dissemination strategy (M7-36).....	33
3.2.1 Planned dissemination means	34
3.2.2 Implemented dissemination tools and activities	35
3.3 Phase 3: Exploitation strategy (M22-36)	40
3.3.1 Planned exploitation means.....	40
3.3.2 Implemented exploitation activities.....	41
3.3.3 Future planned activities	43
4 Operational guidelines	44
4.1 Coordination of IAM COMPACT CDE activities.....	44
4.2 Consortium-level obligations	44
4.3 Graphic identity and EU visibility	44
4.4 Publication procedures	44
4.5 Personal data collection and processing.....	45
4.6 Tracking impact	46
5 Risk analysis and mitigation measures	47
6 Conclusion	49
Annex 1. Networking and synergies	50
Annex 2. Scientific and non-scientific events	53
Annex 3. News and Media websites	56

List of Figures

Figure 1. Mapping between the IAM COMPACT CDE goals and target audiences.....	4
Figure 2. The IAM COMPACT Power/Interest Grid classification.	7
Figure 3. The IAM COMPACT stakeholders’ categorisation in the Power/Interest Grid.	8
Figure 4. The IAM COMPACT website.....	22
Figure 5. IAM COMPACT on Social Media	23
Figure 6. IAM COMPACT on YouTube.....	24
Figure 7. The IAM COMPACT logo	26
Figure 8. The IAM COMPACT colour palette.....	26
Figure 9. The IAM COMPACT flyer and leaflet.....	27
Figure 10. The IAM COMPACT poster and roll-up.....	28
Figure 11. The IAM COMPACT standard presentation.....	29
Figure 12. Working documents templates	29
Figure 13. IAM COMPACT infographic devoted to COP28	30
Figure 14. The I ² AM PARIS modelling platform.....	36
Figure 15. Promotional visuals for the IAM COMPACT capacity building workshops.....	42
Figure 16. The IAM COMPACT exploitation roadmap.....	43
Figure 17. The monitoring system for tracking CDE activities	46

List of Tables

Table 1. Key messages analysis.....	4
Table 2. Roles of key stakeholder groups in the CDE activities.....	8
Table 3. Overview of the CDE tools.	9
Table 4. Implementation timeline.	11
Table 5. Expected outcomes and impacts.....	12
Table 6. Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact.....	13
Table 7. CDE performance indicators.	17
Table 8. The three pillars of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan	19
Table 9. Summary of the IAM COMPACT communication strategy.	20
Table 10. IAM COMPACT on Social Media.....	23
Table 11. Summary of the IAM COMPACT Social Media Summary.....	24
Table 12. Examples of complementary topic-oriented hashtags	25
Table 13. Social Media campaigns planning.....	25
Table 14. IAM COMPACT newsletter/press release distribution	31
Table 15. GA meetings organised since the beginning of the project.....	32
Table 16. Summary of the IAM COMPACT dissemination strategy.....	33
Table 17. Core working groups workshops	36
Table 18. List of external events IAM COMPACT and third party events	38
Table 19. Summary of the IAM COMPACT envisaged exploitation strategy	40
Table 20. Policy briefs.....	42
Table 21. Capacity-building workshops	42
Table 22. Risk analysis according to the Grant Agreement.	47
Table 23. Indicative list of relevant EU funded research projects	50
Table 24. Indicative list of relevant networks and consortia.....	51
Table 25. Online collaboration platforms	52
Table 26. Indicative list of relevant scientific and non-scientific events.....	53
Table 27. Indicative list of leading news and media channels	56

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Description
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution License
CCG	CLIMATE COMPATIBLE GROWTH
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation
CINEA	The European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CO2	Carbon dioxide
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ECEMF	European Climate & Energy Modeling Forum
EMF	European Modeling Forum
EI	Expected Impacts
EMP-E	Energy Modelling Platform for Europe
EO	Expected Outcomes
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GST	Global Stocktake
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
IAMs	Integrated Assessment Models
IAMC	Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium
IEA-WEO	International Energy Agency-World Energy Outlook
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
AR7	7 th Assessment Report of the IPCC
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
M	Month
M.A.T	Messages, Audience, Tools
NDCs	Nationally Determined Contributions
Openmod	Open Energy Modelling Initiative
PRM	Policy Response Mechanism
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SHs	Stakeholders
SSH	Social sciences and humanities
SoMe	Social Media
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

IAM COMPACT is a HORIZON EUROPE funded Research and Innovation project that aims to establish a multi-dimensional demand-driven **Integrated Assessment Modelling (IAM)** framework to inform and support the design and implementation of the next-round Nationally Determined Contributions (**NDCs**) and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries, in respect of the Paris Agreement goals. The need to provide policymakers and other stakeholders with the “right” information and the “right” tools is thus the initial starting point.

To deliver on this, IAM COMPACT puts forward a unique interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach to promote the science-policy and science-society dialogue, throughout the research process. This revolves around a key novelty of IAM COMPACT, the **Policy Response Mechanism (PRM)**, seeking to directly engage with a wide range of stakeholders from different disciplines and geographic scales at each step of the modelling process, from guiding policy-relevant research questions to co-designing and evaluating preliminary findings, producing, thus, contributions along the three following dimensions: increase the **policy relevance** and **societal impact** as well as the **ownership** of the research outcomes¹. It is also facilitated by the **I²AM PARIS** open-access and data exchange modelling platform, which will be the main vessel for coordinating, storing, and providing open access to the IAM COMPACT’s modelling processes, so de facto allowing for **knowledge exchange** among international modelling teams and enabling **mutual learning** among heterogeneous scientific communities, the policy community, and civil society.

Given the above, a salient point for IAM COMPACT is to understand which “lever” needs to be activated to make research results useful to the different end-users and what is the best way to unlock this potential. This leads up to the general objectives of the **CDE plan**, which unfold in this document. In brief, these include **identifying appropriate audiences, when and how to interact with them** to inform the scope of research and share knowledge and **choosing the best techniques** for delivering the planned communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Furthermore, as the project advances, the CDE plan will indicate **how to progressively maximise efforts**, moving from raising awareness of IAM COMPACT to cultivating the most favourable conditions for the **wider uptake** and the **sustainability** of its scientifically significant outputs in the foreseeable future.

The CDE plan is a key output of **WP6** within the **“Explaining”** component of IAM COMPACT, intended to strengthen the link between communication, dissemination and exploitation activities and the policy analysis and capacity development components. As such, it is cross-cutting to all other WPs and will enable communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the whole IAM COMPACT results in the most effective way. It follows that all the IAM COMPACT partners are expected to get involved in and contribute to most of the CDE tasks, ensuring that the work done within the whole project is brought to the attention of, and where possible actively involves, as many relevant audiences as possible.

1.1 Objective and scope of the deliverable

The CDE plan of IAM COMPACT is a living document guiding the communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts carried out by the IAM COMPACT partners and will be updated and adjusted as the project progresses. This is the first strategic update that accounts for and reports on the state of play of the entirety of the CDE activities carried out in the first 18 months of the project.

This Deliverable aims to formalise the plan outlined during the first version (D6.1) and to provide the basis for both external and internal communication and dissemination activities for the remaining duration of the project - with the final update being delivering near the project closeout (M36)-, while articulating the post-project approach

¹ More on Policy Response Mechanism can be found in Heussaff, C. (2022), *Stakeholder engagement plan. (D2.1)*. IAM COMPACT. https://www.iam-compact.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/D2.1%20Stakeholder%20Engagement%20Plan_v1.00_SUBMITTED.pdf

to the exploitation of the produced knowledge and results. A primary objective is to develop a transparent understanding of the way in which IAM COMPACT will be reaching its target audience, with the right messages at the right times and through the right combination of the most profitable information distribution means and activities. Additionally, a key goal is to propose well in advance actions towards an early exploitation strategy, with special focus on activities to maximise the IAM COMPACT's expected impact and boost the project's future sustainability by prescribing the most effective scientific, economic, political, and societal routes, for the continuation of projects outcomes and results after the funded period. Finally, it indicates the way in which efforts will be coordinated and monitored along the entire IAM COMPACT consortium to ensure consistency and quality in their actual execution.

On that basis, this deliverable elaborates on the range of the activities planned within the IAM COMPACT CDE strategy, and the tools already developed or planned, for delivering the appropriate messages to the target audiences. At the same time, it presents the dissemination material produced thus far, both printed—respecting minimum printing principles and choosing such options only when necessary—and electronic and lists several relevant actions to be performed, most of them focusing on knowledge and information exchange (e.g., scientific conferences and publications, etc.). The report concludes by describing the general management process that will guide the implementation of the CDE plan for the upcoming period, also presenting the internal mechanism for monitoring the impact of the planned activities, in terms of attaining a set of predefined KPIs (Key Performance Indicators).

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

Apart from the first introductory section, the remainder of the document is structured as follows:

Section 2	Provides an overview of the overall concept behind the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, focusing on three key strategic elements, the target audience, the key messages, and the tools to be employed per each identified group of stakeholders. In addition, it presents the long-term objectives that IAM COMPACT expects to achieve through the implementation of the proposed CDE plan and reports on the effectiveness of the CDE implemented CDE activities against the set of criteria and indicators set for that purpose.
Section 3	Moves towards implementation, describing the methods and actions through which communication and dissemination strategies are or will be rolled out, while further considering steps towards steering IAM COMPACT's approach to exploiting and making concrete use of its significant scientific results for political and societal purposes in the light of the Paris Agreement.
Section 4	Defines measures and guidelines for the IAM COMPACT consortium partners to consider when communicating, disseminating, and exploiting the project's results.
Section 5	Lists several risks regarding the implementation of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan along with their corresponding mitigation measures, as they are identified in the Grant Agreement (GA).

The document closes with the conclusion remarks summarising the main points around the selected methodological CDE approach.

2 The IAM COMPACT CDE plan

The IAM COMPACT CDE Plan is a periodic report that provides guidelines on the different planned CDE activities and their implementation timeline, defines responsibilities for each planned CDE activity, identifies a selection of supporting communication and dissemination tools and channels and outlines exploitation activities that will foster the adoption of IAM COMPACT's results, methodological novelties and policy implications by different stakeholder groups both during and beyond the project life. It also addresses stakeholders' engagement activities with a special focus on motivating participation and inclusion of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders, who can directly benefit and be benefited by IAM COMPACT. All the information to be used for CDE purposes will be tailored to these target audiences and will be delivered to them through specific CDE means following a two-way exchange for reaching excellence in terms of both academic outputs and societal relevance.

2.1 A brief overview of the CDE strategy

The IAM COMPACT CDE strategy follows a tailor-made approach that builds on the **M.A.T.** technique that aims to achieve appropriate matchmaking of the **M**essages that need to be delivered, the **A**udience they target and the **T**ools to be used to drive a positive impact result. This is done by answering a few simple questions such as:

- "What", for defining the intended messages/information to be delivered,
- "Why" for defining the desired/expected CDE outputs,
- "Whom", for defining the audience that might be interested in or may use these messages/information,
- "When", for defining the appropriate timeline of the planned activity,
- "How", for defining potential different routes for delivering the intended messages/information.

Once that is done, the rest of the CDE plan involves only two more steps, which are:

- implementing the CDE plan and the various CDE activities according to the adopted timetable,
- evaluating the CDE efforts and adjusting the plan's activities accordingly.

In practice, such an approach is expected to facilitate a simple, yet efficient, implementation of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan. First, it will amplify partners' contributions, acting as a checklist for directing CDE efforts to more relevant and important areas and through the proper promotional routes. Second, it will ensure flexibility and adaptability, tailoring CDE activities and communication to project findings. Most importantly, it will facilitate a proactive stakeholder engagement, bringing together an international body of selected stakeholders, such as policymakers, modelling teams and specialised networks, to support the design of a multi-dimensional set of climate and energy policies to help meet the Paris Agreement goals.

2.1.1 Messages (What/Why)

This pillar focuses on activities that could create an interesting story around IAM COMPACT by transforming the project’s vision into intended messages and then into definable actions. The goal is to guarantee that there is a consistent, specific and clear messaging to the project’s stakeholders going forward, **fostering awareness** and **generating understanding** around its long-term expectations and objectives. Beyond that, **engaging target audiences** in the creation and use of the project’s research results, while **ensuring** their eventual **impact**, is underlying every CDE planned activity.

Figure 1. Mapping between the IAM COMPACT CDE goals and target audiences.

There are at least eight high level messages that are foreseen already from the early stages of the project. Each of them represents a specific area of attention. During the first year of the project’s lifetime these messages served as a guideline of the CDE activities, which aimed to ensure their relevance with the broad mission statements of IAM COMPACT. These messages, along with their main derivatives and the CDE-related objectives are presented in **Table 1** below.

Table 1. Key messages analysis.

	Key messages	IAM COMPACT will deliver	CDE objectives
1	Under the Paris Agreement, Parties must pursue policies and measures to reduce GHG emissions, by preparing and implementing successive NDCs of increased ambition. Neither the first round of NDCs nor currently implemented climate policies are on track to meeting the Agreement’s objectives while international cooperation in climate action remains limited.	Informed policy analysis to effectively support the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, by deploying a combination of appropriate modelling tools across fit-for-purpose scenarios. Comprehensive and comprehensible results and actionable policy recommendations on policy options to leverage drivers and overcome challenges to enhance mitigation ambitions, which can be owned by countries updating their NDCs and policy planning beyond 2030.	(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding
2	The modelling world has fallen short of its promise to include non-scientists/stakeholders in its activities, despite the need for wide societal and stakeholder support to underpin NDC design.	A collaborative process of knowledge creation that combines scientific and non-scientific bodies of knowledge and contributes to a holistic understanding of the climate-economy systems and interactions. Co-creation activities will be facilitated via the Policy Response Mechanism (PRM), a dynamic mechanism designed to make engagement user-friendly for all stakeholders, regardless of their experience in modelling work.	(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage

		At the same time I ² AM PARIS modelling platform will serve as a central vessel for knowledge exchange among expert and non-expert audiences.	
3	Non-high-income countries do not “own” their NDC commitments, as the modelling required for their NDC is often outsourced to consultancies.	A series of modelling capacity development workshops and novel modelling tools for integrated assessments in a selection of fast developing countries and large emitters (Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine) with the aim to boost in-house capacities to scientifically underpin locally- and demand-driven policy formulation (including NDCs preparation) and broaden ownership on the country context.	(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage (iv) Ensure impact
4	Modelling usually focuses on the supply-side, despite the need to transform the demand-side and the high potential for behaviour and lifestyle changes.	A framing for complementing demand-side research with supply-side insights, by looking at the role of shifting lifestyle patterns and the societal acceptance in the decarbonisation potential and climate action. In doing so, IAM COMPACT expands its research agenda as to link policy/societal needs to modelling work and co-define with societal end-user those modelling requirements that are necessary for understanding the broader spectrum of feasibility and desirability of low-carbon transition and the key drivers towards this change.	(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage
5	Models for climate policy are mostly designed for long-term horizons and are not equipped to study deep uncertainties, structural changes, extreme events, and economic and climate shocks (such as COVID-19).	A novel integrated modelling framework based on a suite-of-model approach, to cover representative cases of a wider range of transition shocks and additional short-run dynamics, such as extremes, disruptive innovation, behaviour change, and sustainable development, which are typically underrepresented in the long-term scenarios design. This new approach accounts for a broader spectrum of uncertainties around the transition paths, providing a quantification of the range of likely effects over short-term horizons, which could encourage the use of such scenarios in policy work in support of the targets set out in the Paris Agreement and in the European “Fit-for-55” package.	(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Ensure impact
6	Climate action needs to be comprehensively assessed, by exploring the co-benefits of working across the broad spectrum of sustainable development.	A diversified portfolio of interlinked modelling tools comprising (sub-) national, regional, and global IAMs and sectoral models that altogether help explore multiple possible paths into the future, covering the large range of issues relevant to climate policy, like effort sharing under the Paris Agreement principles, and synergistic effects across policies corresponding to the different sustainability dimensions.	(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage
7	There is a need for a new interdisciplinary transitions research	An interdisciplinary toolbox coupling IAM results with sectoral models, and	(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding

	<p>agenda that integrates modelling with social sciences, to assess the feasibility and desirability of the transition to net zero, not only in terms of what, but also of when, where, and especially for whom.</p>	<p>modelling with uncertainty analysis tools, able to feed into robust science and policy prescriptions for policymakers to improve the accuracy and vigorousness of their narratives and eventually make more informed decisions considering multiple near-to-long-term scenarios.</p> <p>Robustness of modelling results is also enhanced by incorporating social, political, behaviour, and innovation aspects in models with insights from political and social sciences, providing granular and detailed information about barriers, impacts, drivers, and sequencing of transition.</p>	<p>(iii) Engage (iv) Ensure impact</p>
<p>8</p>	<p>New mitigation and sustainability pathways must be quantified and assessed against baselines, which are representative of real-world policy efforts and ambitions, and not against misleading or unrealistic no-policy/business-as-usual reference trajectories.</p>	<p>An expanded evaluation framework for benchmarking and validating the consistency and robustness of the modelling results based on multi-model diagnostic analyses (in complementary, cascading, interlinked, or inter-comparison settings) on the realism of post-2030 NDCs and long-term strategies against a multi-dimension set of diagnostics/evaluation indicators, including behaviour, innovation, sustainability, and social dimensions, allowing thus the investigation of uncertainty ranges instead of only sensitivities and observable trends.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage (iv) Ensure impact</p>

2.1.2 Audience (Whom)

IAM COMPACT envisages to be the first, truly co-creative climate-economy modelling project, in the sense that the research questions posed are scientifically ground-breaking and demand-driven, the process followed is transparent, comprehended, and legitimised, while the results are societally and politically relevant and can be transformed into practical action. This includes working towards a constructive engagement with a wide spectrum of stakeholders under a two-way deliberative communication process that provides the opportunity to influence the course of the research process as equals, valuing their knowledge, and respecting their limited availability by providing them the flexibility to plan their own involvement.

Depending on their role in IAM COMPACT, target audiences are categorised as **internal** and **external**. The first ones consist mainly of the IAM COMPACT consortium, which is strategically situated in 19 countries all around the globe, and its core synthesis reflects IAM COMPACT’s de facto motivation to enhance cooperation among the international modelling community to provide robust policy prescriptions to policy and decision-makers around the world. Non-high-income partner countries included in the consortium synthesis (Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine) are expected to be given the opportunity to (further) extend their institutional capacity in support of their climate action and assume ownership of their toolboxes, climate scenarios and policies. In addition, this category includes the project’s Scientific Advisory Board, and members of the European Commission directly involved in the project, such as the Project Officer.

With regards to the external stakeholders, they consist of the following broad groups that have been identified early on, at the onset of the project:

- **Policymakers** and **negotiators** from countries/regions represented in the consortium to be directly involved in the PRM, including all EU Member States and members from bodies of the European Commission not directly involved in the project, other European countries (the UK, Norway, and Switzerland), the top 3 emitters globally (China, USA, and India), and selected non-high-income countries

(Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine) with limited institutional capacities to underpin their climate pledges and strategies with modelling science base.

- **Policymakers and negotiators** from other major emitting (e.g., Indonesia, Japan, Canada, etc.) and other non-high-income countries, national mitigation pathways for the post-2030 period will also be produced, to inform policy planning. Additionally, open-access training material for enhancing capacity in IAM COMPACT pilot counties (Sri Lanka, Ethiopia, Kenya, and Ukraine) will be disseminated and uploaded onto the project’s website.
- **Scientists/researchers/academia**, specifically but not limited to modelling researchers and social scientists worldwide, scientists in IPCC processes, and researchers in relevant Horizon EUROPE projects.
- **Members of research consortia/communities**, such as the IAMC, EMP-E, EMF workshops, the Openmod and OpTIMUS networks for open energy and climate-economy modelling, ECEMF, Climate Compatible Growth, the RedMentes Spanish network of energy modellers for sustainable transition, and the Sustainability Transitions Research Network.
- **Industry decision-makers & business associations**, especially from high-emitting industries.
- **Civil society**, including civil society organisations, climate activist groups, and citizens more broadly. Press and media stakeholders are also included in this stakeholder group.

As a next step, the Power/Interest Grid technique was used to group IAM COMPACT audiences based on whether they have high/low sway or influence over the project’s research process and results, including insights, tools and capacities to be developed within it in support of national climate policymaking. For doing so, stakeholders were plotted in a scatter diagram with four quadrants, each of which represents a different “level” of engagement, ranging from the lowest level (“monitor”), through two middle levels (“keep satisfied” and “keep informed”), to the highest level (“manage closely”), as shown in **Figure 2**:

Figure 2. The IAM COMPACT Power/Interest Grid classification.

Based on these categories, IAM COMPACT target audiences and stakeholder groups were clustered within the quadrants (Figure 3), reflecting their ability to positively influence the project, and the level that project outcomes can affect/influence them.

Figure 3. The IAM COMPACT stakeholders’ categorisation in the Power/Interest Grid.

As part of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, this analysis aimed at indicating and understanding the varying roles of each stakeholder group in relation to the overall CDE goals as well as the different steps of the process that each category could contribute to (**Table 2**), based on their direct ability to influence the project’s positioning and proximity in their sector of specialization.

Table 2. Roles of key stakeholder groups in the CDE activities.

Stakeholder groups	Enhance IAM COMPACT visibility	Give feedback on IAM COMPACT outputs	Create exploitation opportunities	Foster collaboration
Internal Stakeholders				
IAM COMPACT consortium	✓		✓	✓
Scientific Advisory Board		✓	✓	✓
European Commission				
External Stakeholders				
Policymakers and Negotiators from countries/regions represented in the consortium		✓		✓
Policymakers and Negotiators from selected non-high-income countries represented in the consortium		✓		✓
Policymakers and Negotiators from other major emitters and non-high-income countries			✓	✓
Modelling researchers		✓	✓	✓
Researchers in relevant EU projects	✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientists in IPCC and relevant processes	✓	✓		✓

Social scientists		√	√	√
Academia	√	√	√	
Civil society, including civil society organisations and climate activist groups	√			√
Citizens	√			
Specialised press and media	√			
General press and media	√			

The above table is based on the current situation, and the underlying analysis is open to future updates and modifications for several reasons. First, new stakeholder groups may also state their willingness to be involved as the project moves forward, or others may wish a greater involvement than the one originally envisaged. In addition, different CDE needs may arise during and beyond the life of the project that were not foreseen at this stage yet. Therefore, the CDE remains flexible to serve different directions to which the project may head to.

2.1.3 Tools (How)

The IAM COMPACT CDE plan differentiates between various CDE tools and activities depending on the nature of the content to be transmitted, the audience to be reached and the type of interaction deemed necessary to ensure a broader distribution of the project's findings and results. The available tools are summarised in the following table (**Table 3**) according to each stakeholder group and elaborated in the following sections of this report.

Table 3. Overview of the CDE tools.

Stakeholder groups (high-level description)	Internal Stakeholders	Policy-makers (countries represented in IAM COMPACT)	Policy-makers (selected non-high-income countries)	Policy-makers (beyond the IAM COMPACT countries)	Scientist/Researchers/ Academia	Modelling consortia/ communities	Industry decision-makers/ Business associations	Civil society	Citizens	Press/Media
CDE Tools/Channels										
Internal communication channels	√									
IAM COMPACT website	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
I ² AM PARIS modelling platform	√	√	√	√	√	√	√			
Logo	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Flyer	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Leaflet	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Poster & Roll-up	√									
Standard project presentation	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Templates for working documents	√									
Social media (So.Me.)	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

Infographics/Videos	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Commentaries, Newsletters/Press Releases	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Policy Response Mechanism (PRM) - Policy steering interactions ²	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓				
Capacity-building workshops	✓	✓	✓							
Open access self-learning material	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
Non-scientific publications (blogposts, articles)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Policy briefs & Reports	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓					
Non-scientific events	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientific publications	✓				✓	✓				
Scientific conferences	✓				✓	✓				
Synergies ³	✓				✓	✓				
EU final conference	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

The IAM COMPACT CDE toolkit will be continuously assessed with the aim of adjusting and enhancing it in relation to the various activities to be developed within the different Work Packages (WPs) of the project. This might include the update and refinement of existing CDE tools or the design and employment of new promotional means ad hoc for the event and the maturity of the IAM COMPACT future results.

2.1.4 Implementation agenda (When)

The IAM COMPACT CDE plan is articulated in consistency with the general IAM COMPACT implementation plan, which is broken down into three phases, a six-month preparatory phase, followed by the two co-creative modelling cycles in support of climate policy (**Table 4**). Each of them further comprises intertwined work across the five IAM COMPACT pillars, “Listening”, “Exchanging”, “Modelling”, “Expanding”, and “Explaining”, and their corresponding work packages (WPs 2-6). This clearly defined timeline allows the rigorous coordination and management of the CDE plan itself, while at the same time ensuring smooth collaboration among the diverse IAM COMPACT key activities, and information flow across WPs with the aim to function as a platform for connecting

² Policy steering interactions are the exchanges with the policymakers and all other stakeholders that take place in line with the two PRM cycles to direct research, and core working groups of various stakeholders to co-create the entire research process, from scoping the guiding policy questions and informing on model capabilities, to defining the modelling ensemble, and discussing/refining results. As such, they form a core activity of IAM COMPACT, which is also expected to serve as dissemination fora where knowledge and information generated will be shared/discussed. More on the PRM operation is provided in *D2.1 - Stakeholder engagement plan*. IAM COMPACT. https://www.iam-compact.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/D2.1%20Stakeholder%20Engagement%20Plan_v1.00_SUBMITTED.pdf

³ As synergies we consider collaborations with existing modelling consortia and platforms (IAMC, EMF, EMP-E, etc.) and other relevant H2020 projects (PARIS REINFORCE, NDC ASPECTS, ECEMF, ENCLUDE, LOCOMOTION, etc.), where IAM COMPACT participate in, as well as project networks/portals (such as <https://climatechangemitigation.eu/>) and future Horizon Europe-funded projects (e.g., CL5-2021-D1-01 or 2022-D1-02).

the numerous tasks and enhancing their uptake and effectiveness through the project.

Table 4. Implementation timeline.

CDE plan timeframe – “Explaining” Pillar				
CDE strategy phases	Phase 1: Communication	Phase 2: Dissemination		Phase 3: Exploitation
<i>IAM COMPACT</i>	Preparatory stage	1 st Co-creative Cycle		2 nd Co-creative cycle
<i>CDE plan</i>	Initial awareness phase	Targeted dissemination phase		Presentation of results
Timing	Month 1-36	Month 7-36		Month 22-36
Methodological Pillars	Listening	Exchanging	Modelling	Expanding
WPs	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5
<i>WP objective</i>	Ensuring policy relevance and ownership	Open & FAIR science mutual learning	Quantitative evidence in support of post-2030 Paris-compliant climate action	Resilient, inclusive and sustainable recovery and development
<i>WP activities</i>	<p>Operation of a PRM</p> <p>Co-creation of the research process and new knowledge.</p> <p>Engagement with policymakers in the EU and other countries.</p> <p>Scoping of policy and stakeholder needs</p> <p>Linking questions to the right models.</p>	<p>FAIR principles.</p> <p>Open protocols.</p> <p>Model coherence, comparability and consolidation.</p> <p>Harmonisation of input data sources.</p> <p>Coordinated scenario design.</p> <p>Open access to new code, papers and databases.</p>	<p>Diverse ensemble (global, regional, sub-/national and sectoral models).</p> <p>Detailed coverage of all sectors and their interlinkages.</p> <p>Multi-model runs & intercomparisons</p> <p>Post-2030 NDCs, (inter-) national scenarios.</p>	<p>Better real-world policy representation in models.</p> <p>Deep uncertainty & disruptive innovation.</p> <p>Holistic context of sustainability, including equity, biodiversity & biophysical limits.</p> <p>Behaviour change, social innovation, gender, sequencing of transition.</p>
CDE plan activities	<p>Raise awareness</p> <p>Generate understanding</p> <p>Incite engagement</p>	Engage and ensure impact		<p>Engage</p> <p>Maximise impact</p> <p>Ensure result’s uptake</p>

2.2 Expected impact and outcomes

From its inception onwards, IAM COMPACT seeks to contribute to the expected outcomes of the HORIZON CL5-2021-D1-01-04 call (EO), as well as the long-term expected impacts (EI) of the broader D1 Destination to support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society and economy enabled through advanced climate science, pathways, and responses to climate change (mitigation and adaptation), and behavioural transformations. These key outputs are presented in **Table 5** below and include:

Table 5. Expected outcomes and impacts.

IAM COMPACT's EOs		IAM COMPACT's EIs	
EO1	Provision of information for the preparation of climate policies and national planning for the post-2030 period, in light of the Paris Agreement goals and the need to reduce global net greenhouse emissions to zero by 2050.	EI1	Advancing knowledge and providing solutions in earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, social science for climate action and better understanding of climate-ecosystems interactions.
EO2	Enhanced international cooperation among the modelling community and other relevant stakeholders to expand the provision of robust in-country advice to decision-makers around the world.	EI2	Contributing substantially to key international assessments.
EO3	Enhanced mutual learning among the modelling, social science, and policy communities to ensure coherence between different tools used to inform climate action, and consistency with the best available and open science.	EI3	Strengthening the European Research Area on climate change.
		EI4	Increasing the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness, and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate change for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders, and citizens.

The IAM COMPACT CDE plan lays out the project's approach to addressing these challenges.

2.2.1 Measuring the expected outcomes and impact

Although the time frame for the aforementioned expectations is to be met by or close to the end of the project, a monitoring system has been developed already from the initial inception of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, as presented in the following **Table 6**. This will serve as the blueprint for tracking the implementation status of the scheduled activities from the second year of the project onwards, once all corresponding results will be made gradually available.

Table 6. Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact.

EO# / EI#	Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact	Planned >	Achieved	Audience
Uptake by countries				
EO1	Long-term mitigation pathways and advice for the EU and countries represented in IAM COMPACT (top 3 emitters, four non-high-income countries)	8	<i>In progress</i>	Policymakers.
EI1	Countries within and outside Europe acknowledging the project in the development of national energy and climate action plans.	10	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
EI1	Top major emitters publishing NDCs based on evidence co-developed with stakeholders within IAM COMPACT.	4	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
EI1	Non-high-income countries publishing NDCs based on evidence co-developed with stakeholders in IAM COMPACT.	4	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
Project acknowledgement				
EO2	No. of citations of the advancements for expanded integrated assessment modelling capabilities.	100	<i>Too early to assess this indicator</i>	Scientific community, IAM community.
EO2	No. of citations of the new set of diagnostics/evaluation indicators and protocols for model validation and integration published & used widely in modelling research	50	<i>Too early to assess this indicator</i>	
EI1	EC cites evidence from project outputs on the design of its post-2030 climate policy, including interactions with SDGs, and its post-pandemic responses (including in various EC dialogues, fora, and workshops organised by the EC).	N/A	<i>Outside project duration</i>	Policymakers in the EU, European scientific community.
EI2	No. of references to project outputs in IPCC AR7 and/or upcoming special reports.	30	<i>Outside project duration</i>	IAM community, Modelling networks and consortia.
EI2	No. of new scenarios submitted to IPCC AR7 and/or special reports.	≥200	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
EI2	Project acknowledgement in UNEP's Emissions Gap reports.	N/A	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
Policy-related reports, and non-scientific publications				
EO1	Policy briefs for EU & partner countries	10	2	Policymakers, Scientists/Researchers/Academia.
EO1	Reports on national, regional & global mitigation pathways for the post-2030 period (D4.5; D4.6)	2	1	
EO1	Reports on sectoral & cross sectoral aspects (D4.7; D4.8)	2	1	
EO1	Reports on sub-national deep-dives in Europe (D4.9; D4.10)	2	1	
EO1	Report on green recovery/Impact analysis of COVID-19 recovery strategies (D5.1)	1	1	
EO1	Reports on social & gender implications of Paris-compliant climate action (D5.2; D5.3)	2	1	
EO1	Reports on resilience against extraordinary extremes (D5.4; D5.5)	2	1	
EO1	Reports on social disruptive innovations & behavioral change (D5.6; D5.7)	2	1	
EO1	Reports on climate action & sustainable development (D5.8; D5.9)	2	<i>In progress</i>	
EO2	Reports on stakeholder co-created research questions (PRM) (D2.2; D2.3)	2	1	
EO2	Reports on transparent, multi-layer co-creation of the two cycles (PRM) (D2.4; D2.5)	2	1	

EO# / EI#	Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact	Planned >	Achieved	Audience
EO2	Reports translating policy needs into scenario frameworks (PRM) (D4.1; D4.2)	2	1	Civil society, Non-academic audiences.
EO2	Reports on orchestrating (MS4) and implementing innovative synergies with other projects (D3.10)	2	1	
EO3	Reports on open data management (D3.2; D3.3)	2	1	Modelling Community, SSH scientists, Policymakers (EU regional, national, local).
EO3	Reports on the open science protocols guiding the project (D3.6; D3.7)	2	1	
EO3	Reports on global and national sectoral drivers, barriers, and policies (MS5; D6.6)	2	1	
EO3	Reports on the two upgrades of I ² AM PARIS with new models, new features, and new workspaces (D3.8; D3.9)	2	1	
EO3	Report on a new set of model evaluation & diagnostics indicators (MS7)	1	<i>In progress</i>	
EO3	Policy catalogue shared with the modelling community in I2AM PARIS (MS9)	1	<i>In progress</i>	
EO3	Reports on interdisciplinary dialogue for modelling integration (D3.4; D3.5)	2	1	
EI4	No. of non-academic articles in the Press reaching out to society	≥10	11	
Scientific publications				
EO1	Scientific publications on national/regional & global post-2030 pathways considering extreme events, disruptive changes, societal innovations, gender, SDGs.	20	6	Scientific Community
EO2	Scientific publications on national & global mitigation pathways jointly produced with other research projects & non-consortium teams.	15	9	
EO3	Scientific papers on inter-/trans-disciplinary model science including SSH insights	≥12	6	
EO3	Consortium-wide scientific publications on inter-/trans-disciplinary model science including SSH insights.	≥10	6	
EO3	Scientific publications on interdisciplinary modelling science frameworks.	2	1	
EO3	Submissions to modelling consortia (IAMC, EMF, EMP-E, etc.) meetings	≥10	8	
EO3	Presence in conferences	≥25	12	
Advancements to expand the modelling comfort zone and state-of-the-art in integrated assessments				
EO1	Report on a novel multi-model study framework (MS10)	1	<i>In progress</i>	IAM/modelling community. SSH scientists
EO3	New open modelling tools (D6.7; D6.8) & accompanying training material (MS6) for 4 non-high-income-countries.	7	<i>In progress</i>	
EO3	Climate-economy modellers and social scientists brought closer, using project's framework for inter- and trans-disciplinary model science including SSH insights in various projects	≥5	1	
EI3	Open national/regional models exploited by IAM teams after the project ends	≥10	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
EI4	Harmonisation & model integration/evaluation protocols established in modelling society.		<i>Outside project duration</i>	
Stakeholder Database				
EO2	Total	2,000	<i>In progress</i>	

EO# / EI#	Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact	Planned >	Achieved	Audience
EO2	No. of academia (at least 10%).	200	<i>In progress</i>	All stakeholder groups.
EO2	No. of business (at least 10%).	200	<i>In progress</i>	
EO2	No. of industry (at least 10%).	200	<i>In progress</i>	
EO2	No. of civil society (at least 10%).	200	<i>In progress</i>	
EO3	No. of modelling researchers.	200	<i>In progress</i>	
EO3	No. of social scientists.	100	<i>In progress</i>	
EO3	No. of policymakers.	200	<i>In progress</i>	
EO3	No. of local stakeholders (modelling, ministry etc) from 4 non-high-income countries.	50	<i>In progress</i>	
I²AM PARIS platform active support/exploitation and models documentation				
EO2	No. of modelling teams worldwide using the platform.	50	52	Modelling community.
EO2	No. of consortium models' documentation in non-technical language for all audiences.	25	25	All stakeholder groups.
EO2	No. of non-high income countries using modelling applications developed in the project.	4	<i>Too early to assess this indicator</i>	
EO2	Level of Increased confidence (satisfaction) in modelling results across members of the policy steering groups (satisfaction survey results at the beginning and the end of the project).	80%	<i>In progress</i>	Policy steering groups.
EO3	Increased understanding of modelling concepts among policy steering groups member (survey at the start and the end of the project).	50%	<i>In progress</i>	All stakeholder groups.
EO3	No. of I ² AM PARIS workspaces with interdisciplinary insights (including from SSH).	5	<i>In progress</i>	
EI4	No. of new workspaces explained in the I ² AM PARIS platform.	10	2	
EO3	No. of updates of the I ² AM PARIS platform with new models, new features, new workspaces.	2	1	Scientific community (H2020 and Horizon EUROPE projects), IAM/modelling community.
EI3	No. of Horizon projects supporting I ² AM PARIS platform's operation.	5	5 (<i>Outside project duration</i>)	
EI3	No. of climate mitigation models supported by I ² AM PARIS.	70	51 (<i>Outside project duration</i>)	
EI3	No. of IAM teams exploiting open national/regional models after the project ends.	10	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
External events				
EO2	No. of events jointly held in collaborations & synergies with other/sister research projects.	10	2	Modelling community, Policymakers, Industry decision-makers, Civil society.
Stakeholder engagement				

EO# / EI#	Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact	Planned >	Achieved	Audience
EO3	Increased understanding in modelling concepts among policy steering group members, measured at the start and end of the project through a survey	>50%	<i>In progress</i>	Stakeholders

2.2.2 Key performance indicators (KPIs)

Monitoring the effectiveness of the CDE planned activities over the entire lifetime of the project is essential, as it allows to pinpoint actual strengths and weaknesses of the strategy pursued, and to identify and implement corrective actions, when necessary. The monitoring of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan is based on a set of specific time-bound targets which are essential for the overall effectiveness of the engagement of the project with our target audiences (**Table 7**). Each of these targets encompass a set of traceable objectives and straightforward actions arranged under the three major pillars of the IAM COMPACT CDE strategy: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation.

Table 7. CDE performance indicators.

Activity	Objectives	Audience	Monitoring Tool	CDE Indicator	Planned >	Achieved
IAM COMPACT visual identity	Creating distinctiveness and appeal of the project.	All SHs groups	Summary of all monitoring means			✓
Enhanced I ² AM PARIS platform & model documentation	Facilitating harmonisation of data & modelling. Fostering stakeholder co-creation of modelling assumptions, parameters & scenarios.	Policy, industry, academia	Google Analytics; GitHub metrics (viewers, forks, etc.)	Unique users/year	3,000	4,900
				Return of visitors	40%	20%
				Bounce rate	<50%	60%
Project website	Aiming to present and disseminate the project's results as well as to be a referenced source with useful material and links related to the climate debate.	All SHs groups	Google Analytics (set up when the website launched)	Unique users/year	3,000	3,500
				Return of visitors	40%	13%
				Bounce rate	<50%	46%
Commentaries, briefs, newsletters (monthly)	Creating awareness and informing stakeholders on progress; reports and commentaries of policy interest.	All SHs groups	Email monitoring system; Website download analytics	No. of recipients/downloads	4,000	1,019
				Opening rate	30%	47%
Social Media channels	Creating awareness and familiarity with the project topic, objectives, results among policymakers, citizens, scientists & other groups.	All SHs groups	LinkedIn analytics	#iamcompact use on SoMe	1,000	669
				LinkedIn followers	500	839
Infographics & Videos	Creating awareness and familiarity with project objectives & results (especially among non-experts).	Civil society, policymakers	YouTube/Instagram statistics; No. of downloads	Videos views	1,500	1,835
				Infographics downloads/views	400	783
Open access self-learning training material	All the training material developed in Task 6.5 is publicly available & used in case-study countries and by stakeholders.	Young modelling teams	Google Analytics	Downloads/training kit	100	In progress (material released just now)
Blog posts, press releases, articles on news sites	Articles on climate, energy, environment, biodiversity, sustainability in leading news/media websites/blogs.	Civil society	Media monitoring; Copies of articles shared on the website	No. of articles/press releases	15	11

Activity	Objectives	Audience	Monitoring Tool	CDE Indicator	Planned >	Achieved
Networking activities with EU projects under the same or relevant topics	Creating awareness of the project and sharing results among the energy research, social science, modelling communities.	Academia	Digital monitoring; No. of joint papers & acknowledged projects in papers	No. of references in relevant projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers & project meetings.	20	19
A final EU conference	Sharing the final project results.	All SHs groups	No. of attendees; minutes; photos	Audience (70-100)	70	In progress
Scientific Outreach	Academic dissemination of the project's results (open access).	Academia	Digital monitoring	No. of papers	35	23
				No. of conferences	30	12

3 Management of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan

The IAM COMPACT CDE plan builds upon certain WP activities and tasks, and as such, it is fully supported by all IAM COMPACT partners, each of whom contributes via the routes that are most appropriate to their operational model and expertise. Of course, this necessitates the provision of clear-guidelines and project-wide coordination, two strong components in any strategic communication planning process.

With these additional responsibilities in mind, the IAM COMPACT CDE plan aims to provide partners with the most adequate environment and mechanisms to strategically support the multiple actions taken towards raising awareness about the project and making the produced knowledge and results widely available. These actions cover three key strategic directions:

Table 8. The three pillars of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan

	<p>Communication, which includes information and promotion activities to increase the visibility of the project and explain its intended research to the widest possible audience, including media and the public, in a way that is best understood by specialists and non-specialists alike. Within the project, communication is based on a two-way approach intended at encouraging feedback from external actors and includes inter alia networking activities.</p>
	<p>Dissemination, which incorporates a set of targeted activities dedicated to the public disclosure of project results through appropriate channels, including scientific publications, training, or workshop sessions as well as a series of project events, to ensure their exploitation in practical terms. In this case, the primary audience will be more specialised subjects, such as policymakers at all scales, modellers, and the scientific community.</p>
	<p>Exploitation, which goes beyond dissemination by focusing on turning the produced research results into concrete value and societal impact. This may include actions such as utilising the project's outputs in further research activities or for academic purposes or other societal and policy reasons. Here, there is a wide spectrum of expected results that can be recognised as exploitable, such as policy recommendations or standardised modelling activities.</p>

While the two first two angles of activities are closely interrelated, the IAM COMPACT CDE plan clearly distinguishes between them. In doing so, envisaged actions that are put in place to facilitate the transmission of information vary according to the intended purpose on a case-by-case basis. The same applies to the exploitation activities, which aim at boosting the project's sustainability beyond its lifespan.

Considering these aspects, the IAM COMPACT CDE plan analyses its three integral pillars separately.

3.1 Phase 1: Communication strategy (M1-M36)

The IAM COMPACT communication strategy outlines the overall approach for strategically communicating about the project to the public, including all relevant stakeholder groups, in a simplified language. Being implemented from the very first stage (M1-M6) of IAM COMPACT, the communications strategy is articulated around a more “pedagogical” vision of the project, raising awareness, and aims to gradually present the project as the digital representation of a recognised expert. However, more targeted communication efforts will run throughout IAM COMPACT’s implementation to support dissemination and exploitation.

The IAM COMPACT communication strategy (**Table 9**) unfolds alongside and complements the activities of the “Listening” pillar, in an effort to establish and strengthen the link with the engagement efforts deployed under the IAM COMPACT “Stakeholder Engagement Plan” (D2.1)⁴.

Table 9. Summary of the IAM COMPACT communication strategy.

Short summary of the communication strategy	
Goal(s)	Raise awareness of IAM COMPACT and build up a close relationship with its multiple audiences. Intensify communication with the IAM COMPACT primary stakeholder groups, to gradually engage them in the project’s activities. Pave the way towards the implementation of dissemination strategy.
Activities	Develop and update a dynamic strategy for the project’s visibility and the overall CDE activities. Establish strong presence in Social Media channels and ‘teaming up’ with Twitter/LinkedIn/Instagram climate personalities. Networking and clustering activities with sister/other EU projects under the same or relevant topics. Motivating policymakers, industry representatives, and members of civil society (NGOs, climate activists, etc.) to join the core working groups guiding research.
Core messages	What is IAM COMPACT? Where is it going? What is in it for me?
Target audience(s)	Interested members of the public/non-specialised stakeholders. Non-specialised media and press outlets.
Secondary audience(s)	Specialised stakeholders across the spectrum of policymaking, modelling and the broader scientific community.

3.1.1 Planned communication means

Since the very beginning of the project, several tools and activities were foreseen in support of the IAM COMPACT external communication efforts for public outreach. At a primary level, these included the followings:

Operating the IAM COMPACT website | The IAM COMPACT website is primarily understood as the key and essential channel upon which the communication to external parties is built. For that reason, its technical set up was organised immediately after the project’s official kick-start. For the duration of the project, the website will serve as the main “window” towards the outside world with the aim to increase awareness, attract and engage important stakeholders, and to inform about ongoing achievement and results.

Operating online communication platforms (Social Media) | In addition to the IAM COMPACT website, Social Media (SoMe) channels were established early on, during the first months of the project, and will be used

⁴ Heussaff, C. (2022), *Stakeholder engagement plan (D2.1)*. IAM COMPACT. https://www.iam-compact.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/D2.1%20Stakeholder%20Engagement%20Plan_v1.00_SUBMITTED.pdf

throughout its duration not only for communication but also for dissemination and exploitation reasons. The CDE leader is responsible for operating all Social Media accounts and keeping them alive and updated with the most up-to-date information coming out of the project's development and achievements. Here, IAM COMPACT partners can provide content to be published, based on the progress occurring within the different WPs they participate.

Building the IAM COMPACT visual identity | The visual identity of the project was built under D1.1 - "IAM COMPACT visual identity and website"⁵, and comprises of four main elements:

- the IAM COMPACT logo,
- the colour palette to be used in the project's documents,
- the standard promotional material (flyer, leaflet, poster and roll up banner, and a standard power point presentation), and
- templates for all project's documents.

In short, it provides a standard "look and feel" for the project communication materials, ensuring a consistent and recognizable look from a visual perspective.

Developing additional promotional material | In connection to the communication demands of IAM COMPACT additional promotional material is produced to further support the distribution of information and updates about the project. This includes mainly, but not limited to, videos and infographics as well as newsletters and press releases published at least once a month and/or ad hoc upon preparation of workshops and/or any other event, so they can serve to attract new stakeholders.

Using external communication sources | In order to achieve a broader visibility and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, IAM COMPACT saw value in using various external sources and platforms that will allow easy and targeted diffusion of essential project information, that emphasise the designed methodological pathway towards expected outputs and impact. These sources may vary from IAM COMPACT partners' individual communication channels to other websites dealing with similar topics to those addressed by the project. Communication and dissemination through such channels will take place over the project's lifespan and will become more prevalent once IAM COMPACT delivers its first concrete results.

Organising internal communication activities | The IAM COMPACT communication strategy also entails organising informative events, both internal and external, while enhancing participation in similar activities. More information on these actions is given in the following subsections.

3.1.2 Implemented communication tools and activities

3.1.2.1 Communication tools

The IAM COMPACT website | The IAM COMPACT website (www.iam-compact.eu) is the central online tool for reaching out to a wide audience and facilitate all IAM COMPACT promotional efforts along all three pillars of the CDE plan, communication, dissemination and exploitation. As such, it is designed in an attractive and user-friendly way to simplify the navigation of users.

Its main purpose is to serve as a repository for all public deliverables and other results of the project as part of the IAM COMPACT open access policy. It also provides essential information on the project, such as its concept, objectives, workplan and organisation structure as well as on specific activities, such as organisation of events, news, articles and commentaries, and a number of web documents highlighting the project's progress along all WPs. The latter may range from videos and infographics to policy-related outputs and scientific publications,

⁵ Frilingou N. (2022), *IAM COMPACT visual identity & website (D1.1)*. IAM COMPACT. https://www.iam-compact.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/D1.1%20IAM%20COMPACT%20Visual%20Identity%20%26%20Website_v1.00_SUBMITTED.pdf

which constitute two of the main and crucial outcomes of IAM COMPACT.

It also promotes transparency of the project’s modelling armoury, capabilities, and processes by providing essential background information and direct links to the I²AM PARIS platform. This approach will de facto promote mutual learning among the fragmented modelling landscape, ensuring open exchange of information in the field of integrated assessment, sectoral, and energy modelling.

Finally, as the project progresses, outputs of the IAM COMPACT activities aimed at enhancing modelling capacity and creating new tools for policy support, especially in low-income countries, will be made fully open, with direct links hosted in the project website. To cater for this, separate webpages on the website will integrate all relevant information, including all training material on concepts and tools produced as part of the modelling capacity-building workshops in the four non-high-income partner countries (Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine).

The project website is completely functional since January 2023, and it will remain active for up to four years after the end of the funded period⁶.

Figure 4. The IAM COMPACT website

During the project’s first year, the IAM COMPACT website had 3,500 unique users, with a fair amount interacting or exploring more than one webpage each time (bounce rate: 46%), despite most of the project’s outputs are still under development and some of them not yet published. However, the percentage of returning visitors remains low (13%), compared to the target (40%), which necessitates more actions to be taken towards balancing new and regular website users, and building a more dedicated and loyal audience base. Along with publishing new content regularly, running retargeting Social Media campaigns as a means to sending a “reminder” to first-time visitors is also a great way to keep them engaged. Additionally, content optimisation with stronger keywords (SEO) and hashtags (for Social Media content) that better align with the target audience intended, may work to that effect.

⁶ More information on the IAM COMPACT website, its design and technical and operational features is given in: Frilingou N. (2022), *IAM COMPACT visual identity & website (D1.1)*. IAM COMPACT. https://www.iam-compact.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/D1.1%20IAM%20COMPACT%20Visual%20Identity%20%26%20Website_v1.00_SUBMITTED.pdf

The aforementioned actions will also be supported by the regular flow of the IAM COMPACT newsletter and press releases to a growing mailing list. Here key is the role of the project’s worldwide stakeholder network, which will be actively mobilised as IAM COMPACT moves forward through targeted activities, such as the policy steering groups and capacity-building workshops.

Social Media channels | A strong IAM COMPACT Social Media presence has been established during the first year of the project on different outlets each of which aims at different stakeholder groups. From the onset of the project, the IAM COMPACT Social Media activities are heavily relied on the following platforms:

Table 10. IAM COMPACT on Social Media

LinkedIn, which is used to reach out to a more specialised audience, such as policymakers, modellers and scientific community, within the overall framework of the CDE activities. At the time of reporting, the IAM COMPACT official LinkedIn account (@IAM COMPACT) has 839 followers coming from different disciplines and geographical scales, with an acceptable number of them being regularly engaged with the content posted on it.

Twitter, which is used for sharing short announcements on the IAM COMPACT key news and “teaming up” with influencing climate personalities (policymakers, modellers and researchers) at a pan-European and global level. Press and civic engagement, including both civil society organisations and citizens, is also pursued via the project’s twitter activity. At the time of reporting, the IAM COMPACT official Twitter account (@iam_compact) has 722 followers suitable primarily for communication and dissemination purposes.

Instagram is one of the most popular Social Media platforms for sharing photos and videos. Via its official Instagram account (@iam_compact), IAM COMPACT expects to further promote its brand to the wider public by sharing meaningful and stunning online content that is primarily image-based. At the present time 266 users follow IAM COMPACT on Instagram.

Figure 5. IAM COMPACT on Social Media

The web presence of IAM COMPACT has been enhanced with the opening of its official **YouTube** channel (@iam-compact), which is used to host a wide variety of videos realised in the framework of the research

conducted, such as explanatory videos, interviews or recordings of presentations in public events and keynote speeches etc. Considered as one of the most powerful video-sharing platforms worldwide, YouTube will serve as an important cross-channel communication tool, allowing for the quick and secure distribution of IAM COMPACT’s video-based content to the various aforementioned Social Media tools and networks.

Currently, the IAM COMPACT YouTube channel has 71 subscribers and features 21 videos presenting the project’s diversified portfolio of modelling tools as well as a recorded conversation on the critical issue of “loss and damages”. Most importantly though, it shows a good performance counting 1,835 views so far, according to the most recent YouTube engagement metrics.

Figure 6. IAM COMPACT on YouTube

All Social Media accounts are regularly maintained and updated with on-going activities. In particular, new information is uploaded several times per month, according to the following plan:

Table 11. Summary of the IAM COMPACT Social Media Summary

So.Me. channel	Aim	Plan	Status
LinkedIn	Enhance IAM COMPACT's visibility in the policymaking, modelling-research and scientific community, as well as civil society.	3 posts/week	135 posts 86,682 impressions
Twitter	Enhance IAM COMPACT's visibility in the policymaking, modelling-research and scientific community, targeting also press and civil society organisations.	3 posts/week	210 posts 58,000 impressions
Instagram	Enhance IAM COMPACT's visibility in the civil society.	2-3 posts/week	81 posts 9,599 views and impressions
YouTube	Enhance IAM COMPACT's visibility in the modelling-research community and civil society (mainly civil society organisations).	Ad hoc post, when relevant	22 videos 1,835 views

Social Media management, including content creation and performance monitoring, falls under the responsibility of the CDE leader, UPRC. However, all IAM COMPACT partners are expected to contribute to take the project’s efforts to the next level either by sparking ideas for creating new content based on the latest updates on the WPs, or by regularly interacting with the content posted on each platform. In addition, they are encouraged to use the #iamcompact hashtag whenever posting about the project, which can further enhance engagement.

At the current time, the #iamcompact hashtag has been used 669 times across all IAM COMPACT Social Media channels, including also reposts. This constitutes a good performance against the goal of using it 1,000 times throughout the project’s duration, given that we are on the first year of its implementation.

Considering the power of hashtags in making the IAM COMPACT content discoverable to a captive audience, the #iamcompact hashtag is complemented by more topic-oriented hashtags, as the ones shown next⁷.

Table 12. Examples of complementary topic-oriented hashtags

Topic-oriented hashtags																								
#climate	#climatechange	#climatecrisis	#climateaction	#climatepolicy	#climatechangesolutions	#climatechangemitigation	#energypolicy	#parisagreement	#2030agenda	#NDCs	#SDGs	#sustainability	#sustainabledevelopment	#sustainablefuture	#sustainablelifestyles	#decarbonisation	#netzero	#netzerotransition	#emissions	#energymodelling	#scientificresearch	#openscience	#openaccess	#horizoneurope.

Overall, for the reported period, a number of Social Media campaigns were planned and executed to drive awareness about IAM COMPACT. In short, the overall idea was to decompose IAM COMPACT to smaller yet comprehensive and highly accessible content (announcements, results, breakthroughs, etc.), to spark curiosity and help followers gain clear knowledge about the project, and its objectives and achievements.

Table 13. Social Media campaigns planning

So.Me Campaigns	2022				2023												2024			
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18		
Campaign 1		Introductory posts																		
Campaign 2				Meet partners																
Campaign 3						Website														
						Research Method														
Campaign 4							Project novelties													
							First outputs													
Campaign 5										IZAM PARIS/Models										
Campaign 6													Kenya CBW ⁸							
Campaign 7													Website on SoMe groups SoMe on SoMe groups							
															Conferences (COP28, IAMC23, EGU24)					
Campaign 8															CWG ⁹ insights					
																CBWs Ethiopia Sri Lanka, Ukraine				
Campaign 9																				
Campaign 10																				
Ad hoc					Project achievements, scientific publications, articles, newsletters/press releases															

⁷ Hashtags are adjusted according to the content of the Social Media posts and each Social Media platform specific features. The same applies to key accounts tagged on IAM COMPACT each time, except for CINEA (@CINEA_eu) and the Project Officer. Both accounts are mentioned on every project’s Social Media activity.

⁸ Capacity Building Workshop

⁹ Core Working Groups

¹⁰ To Be Decided

3.1.2.2 Communication activities

The IAM COMPACT visual identity | Developed in the early stages of the project (M4), the IAM COMPACT visual identity paved the way for creating a strong and cohesive “branded” look that will serve as the “ambassador” of the project throughout its three-year lifetime and beyond. Key components contributing that to it are:

The official **IAM COMPACT logo** was inspired by and designed as to reveal the multi-dimensionality of the project. Yet its shares a rather clear and simple style which make it easily conceived and memorable.

Figure 7. The IAM COMPACT logo

For ease of identification, the IAM COMPACT logo will be used at a distinct point in all printed and electronic material of the project following the specific logo usage guidelines that have been produced to that end. Among others, these guidelines introduce the **IAM COMPACT colour palette** that shapes the project’s complete visual identity.

Figure 8. The IAM COMPACT colour palette

To spread IAM COMPACT’s identity across a range of communication collateral, a **standard media kit** was produced in the first four months of the project and was made available for all consortium partners and for public use via the internal online communication system (SharePoint) and the website respectively ([link](#)). It contains a number of **ready-made promotional means** designed to support the project’s CDE activities, as shown next.

- The official [IAM COMPACT flyer](#) presents high-level information about the project, such as a brief description of its scope and objectives, the consortium synthesis and contact details, in English and in all project partners’ languages, to be distributed at conferences, meetings, workshops, or other events within the scientific and policymaking communities.

- The official [IAM COMPACT leaflet](#) with more specific content on the project objectives, methods, and expected results, again in English and all consortium languages, is intended for dissemination mainly among academic researchers, policy and decision makers, and European institutions, at conferences meetings, workshops, or other events within the scientific, industry, and policymaking.

Figure 9. The IAM COMPACT flyer and leaflet

- The [IAM COMPACT poster](#) has a similar content as the flyer, yet it will be modified to provide more updated information on the project's development. The poster will be used as promotional material at different events organised by the IAM COMPACT partners or hosted by other relevant initiatives or the European Commission, so it could be also modified for each case.
- The [IAM COMPACT roll-up](#) is portable and easy to be carried around, and as such it forms a convenient and efficient way to viably advertise IAM COMPACT and make a stronger effect at future events organised either by the project partners or hosted by other relevant organisations. Content-wise, the IAM COMPACT roll-up presents the core aim of the project and includes textual and graphic elements on the I²AM PARIS Platform, Climate Policies, and Co-Creation.

IAM COMPACT

EXPANDING INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT MODELLING: COMPREHENSIVE AND COMPREHENSIBLE SCIENCE FOR SUSTAINABLE, CO-CREATED CLIMATE ACTION

IAM COMPACT supports the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, and the design of the next round of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries. It uses a diverse ensemble of models, tools, and insights from social sciences, integrating bodies of knowledge to co-create the research process and enhance transparency, robustness, and policy relevance.

The project explores the role of structural changes in major emitting sectors and of political, behaviour, and social aspects in mitigation. IAM COMPACT also quantifies factors promoting or hindering climate neutrality and accounts for extreme scenarios, to deliver a range of environmentally effective, viable, feasible, and desirable pathways. Finally, it develops technical capacity and promotes ownership in countries with limited in-house capabilities.

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Join us on LinkedIn: [iam_compact](#) | Visit us at: www.iam-compact.eu

The IAM COMPACT project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101056306.

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Let's stay connected

[iam_compact](#) | [iam_compact](#) | [iam-compact](#)

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Partners: EPU, A! Aarhus University, bc3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE, brtarget, CARTIF, CICERO, Modelling, KTH, POLITECNICO MILANO, TEESlab, Wuppertal Institut, KSE, UNIVERSITÉ DE GENÈVE, Imperial College London.

Figure 10. The IAM COMPACT poster and roll-up

In addition, a [standard presentation](#) with basic information on the project is available for direct use or as template to be regularly updated and adapted to the right audiences.

Figure 11. The IAM COMPACT standard presentation

Last, to embed IAM COMPACT’s identity across communications, several **ready-made templates** have been produced to be used by consortium partners, when creating publicity material on behalf of the project, such as deliverables, reports and/or presentations, newsletters, and press releases.

Figure 12. Working documents templates

Additional promotional material | During the first year of IAM COMPACT a number of videos and infographics devoted to the particular scientific areas covered by the project’s WPs and tasks, were created. In addition, a series of newsletters and press releases communicating in non-technical language the progress that is made by the project are distributed on a regular basis through an electronic mailing list to the IAM COMPACT stakeholder community¹¹.

More specifically, in terms of **videos**, IAM COMPACT has launched:

- 21 short demonstration/tutorial videos produced within the first months of its initiation, to introduce its massive modelling armoury in a plain, digestible and understandable manner. All of them can be watched on the project’s official [YouTube channel](#) or broadcasted via the IAM COMPACT website ([link](#)).
- 1 conversational video with influencing climate activists to discuss the critical issue of loss and damage impacts caused by climate-induced disasters with a particular focus on vulnerable developing countries. The podcast took place on the World Environment Day (June 5th, 2023) and its recordings are available on the project’s official YouTube channel.

With regards to **infographics**, during its first year, IAM COMPACT has produced a total of 10 infographics, with the first 9 of them aiming to raise the awareness of the public on climate change and its impacts, as well as the necessity of future mitigation action in a post-2030 framework. The latest one was devoted to the 28th Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP28) that took place in Dubai from 30 November to 13 December 2023, and was co-produced with Horizon Europe [DIAMOND](#) to publicise the side-event co-hosted by the two projects and the [Hellenic Society for the Environment and Cultural Heritage](#).

Figure 13. IAM COMPACT infographic devoted to COP28

In general, all infographics have been used to feed social media as a modern and attractive means to

¹¹ All this material is also reported in more detail in Frilingou N., Nikas A. (2024), *Scientific & policy outreach (including briefs) (D6.4)*. IAM COMPACT ([Link](#)).

communicate about the project. They can be viewed and downloaded via the IAM COMPACT website ([link](#)).

Regarding **newsletters** and **press releases**, a total of 14 releases is currently realised starting from February 2023 as presented below:

Table 14. IAM COMPACT newsletter/press release distribution

	Month	Newsletter/Press release	Outreach achieved
1	February 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 1	Sent: 18/Open rate: 83.33%
2	March 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 2	Sent: 31/Open rate: 54.84%
3	May 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 3	Sent: 38/Open rate: 63.16%
4	May 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 1	Sent: 37/Open rate: 62.16%
5	June 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 2	Sent: 41/Open rate: 58.54%
6	July 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 4	Sent: 45/Open rate: 53.33%
7	September 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 5	Sent: 109/Open rate: 49.54%
8	September 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 3	Sent: 116/Open rate: 50.46%
9	October 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 6	Sent: 109/Open rate: 50.46%
10	November 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 4	Sent: 107/Open rate: 45.79%
11	December 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 7	Sent: 106/Open rate: 41.90%
12	December 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 5	Sent: 107/Open rate: 41.12%
13	January 2024	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 8	Sent: 107/Open rate: 44.33%
14	February 2024	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 9	Sent: 107/Open rate: 45.15%

Typically, newsletters are sent out once a month and their content include the latest developments of the project as well as recent or upcoming activities, success stories, presentations, workshops, reports, publications, and stories of interest to the media. Ad hoc releases are foreseen upon preparation of workshops and events organised or co-hosted by IAM COMPACT to facilitate engagement. On the other hand, the aim of creating and distributing press releases is to officially share the most important news about the project such as milestones reached, major events organised within the project, or flagship research and development results, and/or to gain press coverage. CDE leader, UPRC, in collaboration with the Project Coordinator, NTUA, oversee such processes during the project duration.

The electronic copy of the newsletters and press releases rolled out are published on the project website ([link](#)), and also promoted on social media immediately after their distribution to the IAM COMPACT contact database. They are also distributed to the [IISD \(International Institute for Sustainable Development\)](#) peer-to-peer mailing lists.

External communication sources | In order to maximise impact of the planned CDE activities, several external communication sources are used to convey IAM COMPACT-related information. First, partners’ websites host announcements and links about the project, several websites from other EU projects and initiatives mention IAM COMPACT.

Furthermore, IAM COMPACT has subscribed to several mailing lists offered by IISD, and it uses them for exchanging news on the progress of its action on sustainable development. In particular, the IISD mailing lists relevant to the IAM COMPACT objectives are SDG News, Climate News and Energy News as well as Africa Sustainable Development News and Asia Pacific Sustainable Development News. As the project unfolds, more IAM COMPACT produced material will be promoted on these channels for dissemination and exploitation purposes, such as reports and policy briefs.

Internal communication activities | Regarding internal communication activities, a two-day hybrid **kick-off**

meeting was held in M1 in Athens, during which an overall overview of IAM COMPACT was provided to participants. During the first day, the focus was on presenting the main information regarding the participating partners and their role in the project. During the second day, a detailed overview of the project’s work plan was discussed in tandem with a detailed analysis of all Tasks in each Work Package (WP). In addition, a set of presentations took place regarding modelling aspects that will affect the project. Furthermore, key actions to support IAM COMPACT’s implementation regarding first year’s deliverables and milestones were agreed upon. Representatives from all the 22 IAM COMPACT consortium partners actively participated in the meeting and highlighted the expertise of their institution as well as their contribution to the project’s aim.

In addition, starting in November 2022 onwards, IAM COMPACT held a series of virtual **internal presentation/workshop sessions**, dedicated to presenting the modelling methodologies, assessing the exploitable potential and/or caveats of each, and identifying ways to reach interested stakeholders. All sessions were recorded and were made accessible for all IAM COMPACT consortium partners via the internal communication system (SharePoint), and for external public on the project YouTube Channel and on the website. The objective was to increase internal understanding of IAM COMPACT and the chances to facilitate ownership of what the project will provide in the short, medium, and long term.

Finally, yet importantly, to further ensure smooth cooperation and interaction, and safe exchange of information within the IAM COMPACT consortium, partners have agreed, and the project coordinator (NTUA) has established, **internal communication channels** -as early as the kick-off meeting-, which mainly include:

- Weekly updates delivered by the project coordinator in the form of an e-mail to inform IAM COMPACT partners about the latest updates regarding the implementation of the project, ensuring that all partners have an up-to-date overview of the project’s progress.
- Monthly Executive Board (EB) remote meetings to discuss project progress and/or any areas of concern which are then followed up with partners, thus ensuring that the project is on track towards achieving its objectives and vision.
- General Assembly (GA) meetings on a six-month basis to enable all partners to monitor all major updates in the project, discuss in detail and agree on the next steps for each Work Package (WP), ensuring that all procedures and objectives set are well-understood and acceptable.

In relation to the GA meetings until now 3 such activities were organised as reported below:

Table 15. GA meetings organised since the beginning of the project

	GA meeting	Dates	Location
1	1 st GA meeting	23-24/02/2023	Online
2	2 nd GA meeting	28/08/2023	Kenya (hybrid)
3	3 rd GA meeting	26-27/02/2024	Online

Processes and tasks for internal communication have already been established since M1 and are coordinated by the project coordinator (NTUA). More information is given in the public report “D1.2-Quality Management Plan”.

3.2 Phase 2: Dissemination strategy (M7-36)

Dissemination seeks to maximise the potential societal, scientific and policy impact of the produced results by sharing them with their potential users, such as peers in similar research fields and policymakers. As such, it incorporates a set of long-term and more targeted activities to allow the knowledge of the community of reference to mature along with the evolution of the project.

The strategic planning and the main steps of our approach are summarised below, in **Table 16**.

Table 16. Summary of the IAM COMPACT dissemination strategy.

Short summary of the dissemination strategy	
Goal(s)	<p>Target qualified stakeholders within the policymaking, modelling-research and scientific community.</p> <p>Promote exchange and open dialogue between IAM COMPACT and the value chain stakeholders to co-create solutions and practices, produce demand-driven “system-level” impacts and potentially consolidate policy recommendations.</p> <p>Implement means for making IAM COMPACT results and novelties available to all identified synergies and for showing expected scientific/policy/societal impact, in favour of their future exploitation.</p>
Activities	<p>Continuous dissemination of results within the policy steering groups (of 3-5 policymakers/exercise) and core working groups (of 10-20 stakeholders/exercise).</p> <p>Knowledge dissemination via:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The I2AM PARIS modelling platform, a vessel of the modelling community, in dedicated workspaces featuring inputs, outputs, explanations, visualisations, and model specs in technical and non-technical language. ✓ Scientific outreach activities, including, but not limited, scientific publications and special issues in high-impact journals and conferences, contribution to scientific assessments (IPCC reports), coordination with other projects, participation in the activities of EMF, IAMC, EMP-E, openmod, etc. <p>Keep updated the scientific community and policymakers, including capacity-building partner governments.</p>
Core messages	<p>Enhance the science-policy interface: Pave the way to an enhanced interdisciplinary and transnational collaboration on IAM-oriented policymaking.</p> <p>Enhance policy relevance: Lay the foundation for being the driving force for policy recommendations societally accepted.</p> <p>Enhance ownership: Share IAM COMPACT experiences, lessons learned and results with the identified synergies.</p>
Target audience(s)	<p>Local, regional, national and European policymakers and stakeholders.</p> <p>Modelling communities and networks.</p> <p>Academia/ Representatives of EU-funded project’s consortia.</p> <p>Specialised/scientific media and press outlets.</p> <p>European Commission (i.e., DG Research and Innovation, DG Energy).</p>
Secondary audience(s)	<p>Industry and business associations</p> <p>Civil society, including general press and media outlets</p>

3.2.1 Planned dissemination means

As foreseen in the first phase of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, the dissemination strategy will make use of a broad range of tailored tools and actions that go beyond typical awareness-raising efforts, to actively involve targeted stakeholders in a two-way feedback process around the produced modelling assumptions and approaches, as a means to provide a reality check on them and ensure high policy relevance. This necessitates the development of an integrated strategy, which combines the following science communication with stakeholder engagement activities.

Enhancing the I²AM PARIS modelling platform | The I²AM PARIS modelling platform was developed under the H2020 PARIS REINFORCE project to facilitate the exchange of inputs and outputs among the international modelling community and was then further expanded to represent sectoral insights (in H2020 NDC ASPECTS), integrating as well social sciences (in H2020 ENCLUDE). In IAM COMPACT, the platform will be enhanced as to include new models and policy support tools.

Initiating the PRM and the first co-creation cycle | The Policy Response Mechanism (PRM) has been initiated at the onset of the project (see D2.1 - Stakeholder Engagement Plan), running through a preparatory stage, and will be carried out throughout the project lifetime bringing together qualified stakeholder groups from differed backgrounds and involving them in an intensive open dialogue with IAM COMPACT. The aim is to enable stakeholders outside the project to provide their knowledge and to co-create the agenda priorities and scope for the project modelling activities. Currently, the first PRM co-creation cycle is well underway via the implementation of a series of policy steering interactions¹² with selected representatives of the policymaking community, as well as the organisation of the first core working groups¹³ workshops, and the responding modelling exercises stemming from the process.

Identifying open access databases and repositories | IAM COMPACT is committed to publishing its scientific and modelling results in open access following European Commission's guidelines. To that end, direct and open communication channels and means, such as open access scientific data repositories and journals will be leveraged. Notably, datasets produced from scientific publications acknowledging the project, are systematically uploaded onto the project's community in Zenodo, providing immediate access.

Disseminating towards the Scientific Advisory Board | Already from its inception phase, IAM COMPACT has established a promising Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) of leading representatives in the field of climate dialogue change and the broader context of sustainable development. Establishing a constant exchange with them is considered a great opportunity for IAM COMPACT to gather sophisticated external insights and to complement expertise coming from the consortium partners. It is expected that this will guide IAM COMPACT to identify necessary adjustments and potential areas for improvement in relation to the implementation and development of the foreseen project activities as well as to uncover new dissemination paths.

Enhancing networking and synergies | IAM COMPACT builds strongly on its networks to enlarge its pool of followers and eventually ensure the broader dissemination of its findings and results. In fact, networking, if used strategically, will allow for a broader engagement, and will ease the creation of a large stakeholder community

¹² Policy steering interactions in each of the two PRM co-creation cycles take place between IAM COMPACT, and the policy steering groups formed to provide policy-relevant insights for the IAM COMPACT research agenda. Policy steering groups are identified from the IAM COMPACT multi-layered stakeholder database and comprise 3-5 policymakers.

¹³ Each core working group comprise 10-20 stakeholders from policy, industry, academia, and civil society, who will be selected by the consortium to represent a diverse set of relevant views from EU countries and project-relevant non-EU countries, as well as relevant industrial sectors and civil society groups. Interactions between modellers and stakeholders in each core working group will allow to further refine the IAM COMPACT research questions, and modelling parameters and assumptions as well as to co-create informed Paris-compliant mitigation pathways and scenarios that are politically and socially acceptable.

around IAM COMPACT. Furthermore, it will enhance the dissemination of the project results to a specialised and professional audience.

Authoring articles (scientific and non-scientific) | Over its duration, IAM COMPACT will actively disseminate outcomes and the knowledge produced within it through a variety of publication activities and means. Depending on the purpose and the target audience, both scientific and non-scientific publication outreaches will be among the core activities of the project. As to this, more than 35 scientific publications and papers are planned, focusing on contributing to IPCC reports and on facilitating activities of the broader modelling community, while significant effort will be put into promoting all new modelling exercises or models developed within IAM COMPACT for future scientific assessments. At the same time, more than 15 non-scientific articles and/or blog posts on climate, environment, energy, biodiversity sustainability and other similar topics are to be produced and disseminated via traditional or online media, including high-calibre blogs and news/media websites, at national, European, and international scale.

Participating in external events | Apart from scientific journals and highly specialised media, partners are invited to submit publications to a number of selected conferences and scientific events, to generate an understanding of the project activities and engage the stakeholders. This will allow us to reach as many people as possible, share our experience and our emerging or completed results, engage in meaningful dialogue whilst asserting IAM COMPACT's key role in co-building the European IAM-oriented policy landscape and its scientific excellence. In addition, participation in public events, such as policy events or other thematically related affairs, organised either internally or externally, will yield a positive public perception of our project and may lead to a wider engagement of different civil actors.

3.2.2 Implemented dissemination tools and activities

3.2.2.1 Dissemination tools

The I²AM PARIS modelling platform | In terms of IAM COMPACT dissemination tools, the I²AM PARIS platform (www.i2am-paris.eu) constitutes the main vessel for providing open access to modelling processes and for allowing relevant knowledge exchange among heterogeneous stakeholder communities. At its current state, the platform provides extensive documentation for more than 50 global, national, and sectoral models that are used to support climate policy, through four diverse interfaces each of which provide relevant information for different use cases and for different audiences. Furthermore, it features and showcases the outputs of core modelling exercises from IAM COMPACT and previous projects through seven workspace components. Related publications and modelling data are also provided along with interactive visualisations of the modelling results, customised for different audiences.

During the project lifetime, I²AM PARIS will be further extended in terms of content and features to support model intercomparison exercises and capacity development activities of the project. Additionally, more enhancements can be potentially applied to accommodate the needs of the IAM COMPACT partners and alongside the development work of the other projects¹⁴.

¹⁴ Most of the envisaged improvements will take place simultaneously with five more projects, the Horizon 2020 projects NDC ASPECTS (<https://www.ndc-aspects.eu>) and ENCLUDE (<https://www.encludeproject.eu>), and the Horizon Europe projects DIAMOND (<https://www.climate-diamond.eu>), TRANSCIENCE (<https://www.transcience.eu/>), and EU-CHINA-BRIDGE, each with a different scope. More details on the envisaged improvements in the context of IAM COMPACT and the upgrade plan are given on D3.8: I²AM PARIS v2.0.

Figure 14. The I²AM PARIS modelling platform

At the time of reporting, I²AM PARIS shows a very good performance, having 4.900 unique visitors coming from the IAM COMPACT activities. Yet metrics on the bounce rate (60%) and the number of returning visitors (20%) indicate that efforts need to be taken towards developing audience loyalty, while balancing new and regular users. These may include further promotion of the platform through a mixture of tactics, including more targeted SoMe activities and SEO optimisation with more targeted keywords to increase the platform’s visibility. It is expected though that the overall performance of I²AM PARIS will increase in the following period since results from the project modelling and capacity-building activities will be published.

The first PRM co-creation cycle | Starting from July 2023, three EU-level and one national core working groups workshops were organised as part of the PRM operation, as shown next:

Table 17. Core working groups workshops

Core Working Groups workshops		Date	Link
1	Optimal Transition (EU level)	20 July 2023	Here
2	Global Effects (EU level)	26 October 2023	Here
3	Behavioural Change (EU level)	31 October 2023	Here
4	National Core Working Groups (India)	6 November 2023	Here

Details on the core working groups’ workshops are provided in the corresponding deliverable D6.4-“Scientific and policy outreach (including briefs)”¹⁵.

¹⁵ D6.4 Scientific & policy outreach (including briefs)

Open access databases and repositories | Recognising and pushing forward the importance of Open Science and the FAIR principles, IAM COMPACT publishes all produced scientific results, including publications and other research material like datasets, in general-purpose, open repositories such as Zenodo and Github. To that end, two project communities have been created on both spaces, the IAM COMPACT Zenodo community, which is reachable at <https://zenodo.org/communities/iam-compact>, and the IAM COMPACT Github community, available on <https://github.com/IAM-COMPACT>.

Both communities will support archiving and sharing primary data outputs from research on modelled-based climate change mitigation and will be further developed for IAM COMPACT's results' exploitation for all user groups. Dissemination outlets, such as [Open Research Europe](#) and [HORIZON Results Platform](#), [offer a great opportunity for open access publications and](#) may also be considered when appropriate.

Disseminating towards the Scientific Advisory Board | From its outset, IAM COMPACT has designed a comprehensive approach to better incorporate its Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) in the project development. This includes regular exchanges of up-to-date knowledge and data on interesting work in the different WPs, which is mainly achieved through fixed reports on the project progress and "ad-hoc" meetings where SAB is invited to participate and offer its impartial advice on the project critical outcomes. In addition, an SAB meeting is usually scheduled in connection to the project General Assembly meetings.

Apart from guiding IAM COMPACT, it is expected that constant exchange with members of the IAM COMPACT SAB will help enhance robustness of the produced results and ensure their European-wide (and beyond) acceptance and usability, a key success factor for IAM COMPACT. To that end, SAB-related activities are carefully planned and coordinated under the project coordinator's guidance.

3.2.2.2 Dissemination activities

Networking and synergies | IAM COMPACT's endeavour to join forces with existing and emerging modelling research projects, modelling consortia and other relevant initiatives is key to delivering on its ambitious work program. Toward effectively strengthening the flow of produced knowledge outside the consortium and across the identified target stakeholder ecosystem, enhancing mutual dialogue and cooperation among associated research communities/disciplines will allow for a multi-dimensionally study and delivery of robust post-2030 climate policy recommendations worldwide, which is inherent in the project's research agenda. In this light, IAM COMPACT is fully dedicated to carry out a high-sounding number of synergetic/joint activities on climate change research.

Starting with mapping "sister" EU project and alliances or stakeholder groups with similar orientations, and identifying ways to reach them, these activities range from information exchange and reports on the project progress, to complementarities and alignment of activities, such as joint publications (briefs, peer-reviewed journal articles etc) and joint submissions to scientific and/or other modelling consortia meetings, such as EMP-E, IAMC, EMF and ECEMF. Participation in information platforms related to the project objectives is also foreseen.

Management and coordination of the IAM COMPACT outreach joint activities during its lifetime is part of Task 3.5 – "Collaborating with and creating synergies among modelling research projects" and a final report will be produced at the end of the project. In the first phase of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, an indicative list of relative EU research actions and modelling communities as well as open collaboration platforms was proposed to facilitate the process. This list is available on [Annex 1](#).

Likewise, for better planning purposes, the IAM COMPACT CDE plan regularly monitors the progress and results achieved in terms of the project participation in activities jointly organised with various networking groups. During its first year of implementation, IAM COMPACT took part in 19 such activities, 12 of which concern **joint scientific publications** and seven **joint participations in scientific conferences**, as reported in D6.4- "Scientific and policy outreach (including briefs)".

All IAM COMPACT's joint scientific activities are available on the project website, [here](#).

Published articles (non-scientific and scientific) | Publication activities offer a major possibility for IAM COMPACT to communicate its scope and objectives (in general), or to specifically disseminate its research results and better reach more targeted audiences. With respect to the first one, IAM COMPACT’s intention is to raise awareness on its research agenda using a non-technical language and public media channels, such as blogs and news/media websites, at national, European and international scale. To that end, in the first phase of IAM COMPACT CDE plan several leading digital news and media outlets that appear appropriate for IAM COMPACT were proposed. The list is available on **Annex 3**.

On the other hand, IAM COMPACT partners are encouraged to develop several scientific papers and articles stemming from the project’s potential exploitable outcomes and methodologies, and to publish them in high-impact scientific journals prioritising fully open access opportunities and working paper series. The project coordinator (NTUA), with the active contribution of all IAM COMPACT consortium partners, has drafted an indicative list of peer-reviewed journals that might be more suitable to the identified topics and to the IAM COMPACT topic research agenda. The list is available on the project’s SharePoint and is regularly updated as part of the activities under Task 6.3 - Scientific publications and academic outreach.

In terms of **non-scientific publications**, IAM COMPACT is currently acknowledged in 11 articles, all of which are reachable via the project website, [here](#). In terms of **scientific publications**, IAM COMPACT has published and/or been acknowledged in 23 papers in total, including the 13 peer-reviewed articles that were jointly produced in the context of the project’s clustering activities, as mentioned earlier. All IAM COMPACT scientific papers are available on the project website, [here](#), and on [Zenodo](#).¹⁶

External events (non-scientific and scientific) | In terms of IAM COMPACT, opportunities to actively take part in external outreach activities, including both thematically associated (non-scientific) events and scientific conferences are continuously sought after.

Until now, IAM COMPACT has organised and/or participated or presented in eight thematically associated **non-scientific events**, with the objective of stimulating the interaction with its concerned stakeholder ecosystem. These participations are presented in **Table 18** that follows.

Table 18. List of external events IAM COMPACT and third party events

	Event	Type	Date	Location
1	EMP-A (Energy Modelling Platform for Africa) 2023	Workshop	11-28.04.2023	University of Namibia
2	Loss & Damage: it could be your turn next	Policy event	05.06.2023	IAM COMPACT YouTube channel
3	Summer School on Integrated Assessment Models	Other	3-7.07.2023	Villa del Grumello (Como, Italy)
4	ICTP Joint Summer School on Modelling Tools for Sustainable Development 2023	Workshop	3-14.07.2023	ICTP (Italy)
5	Climate Targets 2040: Bridging modelling and policy	Policy event	13.09.2023	Bruegel
6	LOCOMOTION Massive Open On-line Course (MOOC)	Workshop	3-13/11.2023	Online
7	IAM COMPACT side-event at COP28	Policy event	5.12.2023	Dubai expo city (Greek Pavilion)
8	IAMC Webinar: Scientific Working Group (SWG) on National Scenarios	Webinar	30.01.2024	Online
Upcoming participations				
1	EGU (European Geosciences Union) Assembly 2024	Other	14-19.04.2024	Austria Center Vienna (ACV)

¹⁶ Details on the articles (scientific and non-scientific) published by IAM COMPACT are provided in D6.4 Scientific & policy outreach (including briefs)

2	42 nd edition of the IEW (International Energy Workshop) hosted by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA)	Workshop	24-25.06.2024	Bonn (Germany)
3	IEA-ETSAP (International Energy Agency - Energy Technology Systems Analysis Program) semi-annual workshop	Workshop	24-25.06.2024	Bonn (Germany)

Information about the external events hosted by IAM COMPACT or third-party organisers is available on the project website, under the “NEWS & EVENTS” webpage, [here](#).

Last, regarding **scientific conferences**, IAM COMPACT has a total of 12 participations, including the seven joint endeavours mentioned previously. Information about them is available on the project website, [here](#).

D6.4 - “Scientific and policy outreach (including briefs)” elaborates all the aforementioned events, both non-scientific and scientific.

3.3 Phase 3: Exploitation strategy (M22-36)

The exploitation phase is dedicated to the successful uptake of scientific results and their actual applicability in support of the Paris Agreement goals. Here, the role of IAM COMPACT consortium partners and their worldwide stakeholder network is of high importance, which will be actively mobilised in the policy steering groups. Furthermore, more concrete actions need to be identified as well as the specific model and strategy for the exploitation of each IAM COMPACT significant result from M22 onwards and up to 4 years after the funded period.

Based on the forecast of IAM COMPACT’s expected long-term results (Section 2.2.1), **Table 19** below summarises a preliminary exploitation agenda. Upon completion of the first year, it will be updated with the subsequent year and so on to properly monitor and evaluate progress.

Table 19. Summary of the IAM COMPACT envisaged exploitation strategy

Short summary of the envisaged exploitation strategy	
Goal(s)	Support the realisation of benefits offered by adopting IAM COMPACT’s results toward relevant target groups, by replicating and upscaling them (external success). Support IAM COMPACT consortium partners to increase experience in their fields and enhance the exposure of outcomes in publications and the press (internal success).
Activities	Authoring policy briefs, business guides and other publications targeting non-academic audiences on robust strategies toward climate neutrality. Modelling capacity development workshops and novel modelling tools for integrated assessments aimed at policymakers and technical staff in non-high-income countries and/or countries with limited technical/institutional capacities. Use of models among the IAM COMPACT ensemble that have long been used in EC policy assessments.
Core messages	n/a -To be defined in accordance with the next sub-objectives: Achieve science-policy interface: Share IAM COMPACT recommendations with national and pan-European policymakers and modelling resources. Achieve policy relevance: Turn IAM COMPACT’s model-based policy novelties into a source of inspiration at a pan-European and global level. Achieve ownership: Facilitate capacity building both in terms of IAMs and in terms of international cooperation and climate policy, focusing on non-high-income countries.
Target audience(s)	Local, regional, national, and European policymakers and stakeholders. Modelling communities and networks. Academia/ Representatives of EU-funded project’s consortia. Specialised/scientific media and press outlets. European Commission (i.e., DG Research and Innovation, DG Energy).
Secondary audience(s)	Industry and business associations Civil society, including general press and media outlets

3.3.1 Planned exploitation means

For the successful implementation of its exploitation plan, IAM COMPACT counts on the various forms of communication and dissemination means outlined earlier. Care, however, will be taken towards several already identified activities expected to further facilitate exploitation, with a major focus on meaningful exchanges and engagement with national and European policymakers. Such exchanges will ensure that IAM COMPACT results are both innovative and employed in practice, thus underlying their added value.

Technical/policy briefs and reports | IAM COMPACT will issue at least 10 policy briefs showcasing significant policy recommendations derived from the research process and lessons to inform and contribute to the further

development and implementation of NDCs, and their alignment with the overarching goals of the Paris Agreement. Among others, they will touch upon topics related to future action pledges and long-term decarbonisation pathways of the EU and of other major emitting and non-high-income countries. In addition, one policy catalogue will be produced and shared with the modelling community in the I²AM PARIS platform.

Regarding policy briefs, all of them will be accompanied by their own newsletter to disseminate them to the widest possible audience through the IAM COMPACT consortium, adopting a non-technical language and translated into the language of all engaged communities.

IAM COMPACT is also expected to produce a total of 47 publicly available deliverables, and 10 milestones incorporating scientific results produced throughout the project. All of them will be made available via the project's website and Zenodo, and will be further promoted via social media, newsletters and/or other promotional channels as well.

Regional/Local capacity-building workshops | To broaden ownership of the integrated assessment process, concepts, and tools in Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine, and to support a local and demand-driven coherent policy formulation, a series of capacity development workshops will be organised for each case study country throughout the project's lifetime. Although, both the content and depth of each workshop will be demand-driven, the general structure is designed to include high-level introductory sessions to concepts behind the modelling tools used to support policy, as well as comprehensive hands-on training sessions on the modelling tools. In the end, participants will be guided through the creation of multi-sector and multi-resource country models and applications to investigate planning issues of relevance to the countries and to their NDC preparation.

Apart from the new open modelling tools to be (co-)produced as part of the IAM COMPACT capacity building activities, another significant output will be the production of open-access, standalone sets of teaching and training material for re-use after them for creating new academic courses in the case-study countries and self-learning experiences on well-known platforms such as OpenLearn.

All capacity-building training workshops will be organised under Task 6.5 - "Expansion and development of technical and institutional capacity in pilot countries", led by KTH. Their final format (onsite, online or hybrid) will depend on the needs and constraints in effect, including implications of the COVID-19 pandemic, or of the energy crisis stemming from the invasion of Ukraine by Russia. Overall, these capacity development activities will build permanent capabilities to local partners and communities, providing usable material (including models) that can be used even beyond the duration of the project.

Final EU conference | IAM COMPACT's final EU conference will be held at the end of the project (M36) to present the achieved outcomes to its stakeholder pool with a specific policy side-event. In particular, the intention is that this final conference can be organised in proximity to an international scientific conference, like an ECEMP, or IAMC event, where the outcomes of the project could be shared with the scientific world, policymakers and top industry representatives, including modellers, at a pan-European and international level. It is expected that at least 70 qualified stakeholders will participate in and be informed on the revised global, regional, and national pathways, with clear policy implications and guidelines for strengthening climate action, as well as the novel framework for "expanded, multi-model assessment", expected to result from the PRM and the operation of its two co-creative cycles.

More on the final EU conference will be given in the upcoming revised CDE plan report, planned for month 36.

3.3.2 Implemented exploitation activities

Technical/policy briefs and reports | The first two policy briefs have been issued early on, almost at the beginning of the project and have been made available on the project website [here](#). Both address a wide range of readers with the aim to provide a broad understanding of the capabilities of the models employed under IAM COMPACT as part of the PRM and how these models can be used to support policy planning beyond 2030 for the European Union (EU), while tackling pressing issues, such as replacing Russian gas and their implications for energy sustainability and affordability, respectively.

Table 20 below summarises in brief these two policy briefs, yet more details are available on D6.4- "Scientific and policy outreach (including briefs)".

Table 20. Policy briefs

Policy brief		Issue date
1	Stakeholder inclusion in climate and energy policy making – The IAM COMPACT policy response mechanism.	November, 2022
2	Three responses to the energy crisis – The co-benefits of energy efficiency.	April, 2023

Regional/Local capacity-building workshops | Starting from August 2023, three capacity building workshops were organised and were successfully executed in Kenya, Ethiopia and Sri Lanka. Detailed information about all of them are available on D6.4- “Scientific and policy outreach (including briefs)”.

Table 21. Capacity-building workshops

Capacity-building workshop	Date of implementation	Link
1 Capacity building workshop in Mombasa (Kenya)	29 August-1 September 2023	Here
		Here
2 Capacity building workshop in Addis Ababa (Ethiopia)	23-24 January 2024	Here
3 Capacity building workshop in Sri Lanka	30 January 2024	Here

Upon preparation of the three capacity building workshops a series of promotional activities took place, which included apart from the website posts, email invitations by each organiser to their networks, ad hoc newsletters/press releases and social media promotion detailing information on the scope of each workshop, the agenda, and the registration process. In support of these actions, visual banners were also produced, whereas in the case of Ethiopia, coverage on local and national media was ensured prior to its launch¹⁷.

Figure 15. Promotional visuals for the IAM COMPACT capacity building workshops

¹⁷ <https://www.esi-africa.com/news/kenya-climate-modelling-workshop-to-focus-on-key-energy-issues/>
<https://www.africa.com/iam-compact-a-horizon-europe-modelling-workshop-in-mombasa/>

3.3.3 Future planned activities

From its inception, the IAM COMPACT CDE plan foresaw the early drafting of a preliminary, yet clear-defined strategy describing the “exploitation roadmap” to be followed during the life of the project and beyond. This roadmap is updated in the current version of the plan, considering the following steps and activities:

Figure 16. The IAM COMPACT exploitation roadmap

Moving towards the second PRM and subsequent modelling cycle of the project, next steps will focus on updating the final IAM COMPACT exploitation strategy that will be then integrated into the CDE plan at the end of the third year of the project. To facilitate the process, a special internal seminar is suggested to be devoted to exploring the possibilities for exploitation of IAM COMPACT results, including a technical description and analysis in terms of their imminent potential to be exploited, and each partner’s contribution. The task is scheduled for when a bulk of exploitable project results will be made available (e.g., potentially after the conclusion of the first PRM cycle), and upon agreement with the Project Coordinator and the consortium partners.

4 Operational guidelines

Implementation of CDE activities within IAM COMPACT is a resource-driven and intensive process, meaning that, besides the main implementation coordinator (UPRC), all IAM COMPACT consortium partners are requested to get involved in the ways they consider most appropriate for generating the expected impacts on different levels and according to the background expertise they bring to the project. To that end, the IAM COMPACT CDE plan aims to give an orientation towards ensuring that the consortium will take a proactive role in this endeavour.

4.1 Coordination of IAM COMPACT CDE activities

The main CDE coordinator (UPRC), supported by the WP6 leader (KTH) will be the central point for coordinating the implementation of the activities foreseen in the IAM COMPACT CDE plan. The final approval though will be given by the Project Coordinator (NTUA).

4.2 Consortium-level obligations

While some partners (KTH, Bruegel, NTUA, WI) are directly involved in CDE activities in view of their role in the project, all IAM COMPACT consortium partners should be committed to regularly participating in them by:

- communicating and disseminating IAM COMPACT activities and results to their respective networks, via their institutional website and/or their social media channels (if applicable),
- contributing to the content of the monthly newsletters/press releases or other relevant activities, such as publications, both scientific and non-scientific,
- disseminating results in open-access platforms
- informing the partner responsible for the CDE plan in terms of interesting, related initiatives and events that IAM COMPACT can participate in,
- keeping track of their communication and dissemination activities by filling in a dedicated reporting table available in the SharePoint of the project.

4.3 Graphic identity and EU visibility

Unless the European Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, communication and dissemination of results in any form, including both written and electronic, all CDE tools and activities must refer to and include:

Information on EU funding

Disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate)

As defined in Article 17 of the G.A.

The IAM COMPACT project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101056306.

In addition, they should share the official IAM COMPACT logo and the graphical elements as well as mentioning the URL of the IAM COMPACT website and the social media accounts.

4.4 Publication procedures

Prior notice protocol |

Unless agreed otherwise, any partner that intends to disseminate their results should give at least 15 days advance notice to the IAM COMPACT consortium (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results to be disseminated. In case of no notifications from other partners before the set date, the author(s) may assume that there are no objections to the publication. In all cases whatsoever, confirmation of the right to publish will be subject to the agreement of the project coordinator during the

project lifetime, and openly thereafter.

[Open access to scientific publications |](#)

IAM COMPACT consortium partners are committed to publishing their scientific publications in open access, according to the “Gold” open access model, while publication of special issues will be sought. The policy that will be implemented by the project will also include the “Green” open access model, when applicable in case of e.g., institutional agreements. In all cases, the platform Sherpa/Romeo will be used to provide a summary of permissions that are normally given as part of each publisher's copyright transfer agreement.

Furthermore, the IAM COMPACT consortium will consider submitting papers to [Open Research Europe](#), the open-access publishing platform for research stemming from Horizon EUROPE funding, while all project publications and accompanying data will be stored in the online project community created on Zenodo ([link](#)). All uploads will thus be directly indexed in [OpenAIRE](#).

More details on the IAM COMPACT publication policies and protocols will be offered under Task 3.1 – “Exchange requirements specifications and data management” and its corresponding deliverables (D3.2-D3.3).

[Open access to scientific data |](#)

IAM COMPACT will collect relevant research data that will be managed according to the Data Management Plan (D3.2-D3.3), in line with the FAIR principles and under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights. In the case of monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial uses and derivative works.

[Intellectual Property Rights \(IPRs\) |](#)

CDE activities in IAM COMPACT are deeply wedded with Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) protection, which is clearly stated in the Grant Agreement (Article 16 and Annex 5). In short, key elements relating to IPR include recognition of the overriding authority of the EC contract, specification of conditions of knowledge access and use, protocols, and plans for data collection in accordance with EU data policy and specification of both excluded and required knowledge relevant to the project. In terms of ownership of new knowledge generated during the research, can be transferred to the EC free of charge and without restriction on use/dissemination (Clause 29).

At the same time, unless published as a Special Issue of a scientific journal relevant to the scope of IAM COMPACT, the copyright of reports will be with the IAM COMPACT consortium. Thereby, in the case of quoting texts, a proper reference to the report will need to be made along internationally agreed lines.

4.5 Personal data collection and processing

Throughout all data collection activities, IAM COMPACT consortium partners will adhere to the established EU Regulation (2016/679) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data (GDPR). In this regard, they must ensure that all personal data collected and/or analysed from the participating stakeholders is:

- processed lawfully and fairly, in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects and in a manner that ensures appropriate security,
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date in a form, which permits the identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed

Accordingly, to ensure compliance, all personal data to be collected will be limited to information such as name, email, institution, stakeholder group, and country, and based on the owner's consent or option to change their mind and withdraw from the IAM COMPACT stakeholder database. Furthermore, IAM COMPACT will focus first on the already established networks (e.g., associations, platforms, etc) from project partners, past activities/projects or ongoing related projects. In all cases, whatsoever, and where appropriate subject to regulatory constraints or

restrictions and licensing issues from the owners of the data, the data and their metadata description will be anonymised.

4.6 Tracking impact

Given that monitoring and evaluation stand as a fundamental pre-condition for achieving the strategic CDE performance goals as established at the onset of the project, IAM COMPACT consortium partners will provide information on their CDE activities in at least a two-month interval and according to the monitoring system developed under this deliverable. In short, this system consists of two main excel-based tools—a consortium-wide “CDE monitoring table”, available to all IAM COMPACT consortium partners for recording their CDE efforts and a “Consolidated CDE monitoring table” intended for use only by the IAM COMPACT CDE plan leader (UPRC). The latter will integrate all information provided by IAM COMPACT consortium partners with respect to their individual CDE activity.

The two tools follow the same design pattern, yet the second one bears an internal mechanism for relevant statistical data generation and export (**Figure 17**).

Figure 17. The monitoring system for tracking CDE activities

5 Risk analysis and mitigation measures

Risks regarding the implementation of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, thus reaching the expected objectives, have been identified at the onset of the project and are included in the Grant Agreement. They are all presented next, along with their corresponding mitigation measures.

Table 22. Risk analysis according to the Grant Agreement.

Type of risk	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation measures
IAM COMPACT consortium partners' low contribution.	Low	High	Rigorous project management. Failure of individual participants will lead to an immediate assessment of capabilities and task reassignment. Partners have an adequate range of technical skills and can take over tasks if needed.
IAM COMPACT consortium partners' Delayed contribution to outputs.	Medium	Low	These actions refer to the internal adjustment of the tasks and have no impact on delays in submitting related deliverables to the Agency/EC. Even though, quality management, including early directions for timely outputs, and well-organised monthly calls (reviews/appropriate revisions) will ensure their effective implementation.
Low scientific and technical quality of IAM COMPACT deliverables.	Low	High	Rigorous quality management. First deliverable drafts are to be submitted one month prior to their deadline, for thorough internal review, including detailed feedback by Coordinator and 2-5 reviewers. All IAM COMPACT consortium partners have an excellent track record for scientific quality.
Lack of coordination with other actors and wrong expectations.	Low	Medium	Acknowledging challenges associated with the scientific paradigm to date and the requirement of inclusiveness in the climate dialogue, IAM COMPACT is oriented on co-creation with stakeholders (WP2).
Limited participation of external experts.	Medium	Low	Robust and rigorous CDE plan elaborated in Task 6.1, promoting project (outcomes) with all possible means. Besides that, to maximise participation, IAM COMPACT will use existing know-how in establishing an effective communication platform.
Difficulty in organising capacity development activities.	Low	Medium	It is foreseen that European partners can join planned webinars and workshops remotely and for that reason IAM COMPACT will use state-of-the-art tools in a highly efficient manner, to activate discussions and stakeholder feedback. Almost all IAM COMPACT consortium partners have relevant experience of the last 1.5 years.
Limited policy impact due to COVID-19 and delays to major policy or science processes.	Low	Medium	The general project planning fits well in the policy schedule. If COP sessions are further delayed (as with COP26) and GST or IPCC/other processes are affected, the envisaged impact is partly beyond the project duration. In addition, the COVID19 pandemic is seen as a "research opportunity" to use models in extreme/disruptive conditions.
Vulnerability of modelling to different types of uncertainty.	Low	Medium	Robustness of modelling is a core aim (multi-model inter-comparisons) of IAM COMPACT, with further enhancing the robustness of outcomes against uncertainties being one of the core IAM COMPACT WPs (WP5). Within it, the following activities are foreseen: (i) Pioneering new scenarios that better represent extremes, disruptive innovation, and behaviour changes in models, will be tested through

Type of risk	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation measures
			hindcasting on empirical data. (ii) A novel model inter-comparison framework will be developed.
Limited legitimacy of models, methods, and tools.	Low	High	Technical/policy briefs on model capacity are foreseen. Modelling activities will be carried out in an open access platform, and their specifications will be co-defined with policy/stakeholders, who will also drive modelling processes and co-develop modelling needs.
Limited contribution to major international scientific assessments (e.g., IPCC reports).	Low	Medium	IAM COMPACT consortium partners already participate in networks supporting assessments (IAMC, EMF, etc.). Among them, 11 partners are IPCC AR6 authors, while others participate in several project models that directly contribute to IPCC AR6. In addition, SAB features personalities with a remarkable track record in IPCC reports that can steer efforts to support climate dialogue.
Partners in conflict areas unable to perform due to the conflicts and/or particular geopolitical situation (e.g., invasion of Ukraine by Russia, etc.).	Medium	Medium	Online capacity development and training activities will be pursued with partners located in conflict or otherwise geopolitically sensitive areas if physical interactions are infeasible. The project will keep flexibility throughout its two co-creative cycles and shift capacity development and policy/scientific processes appropriately to ensure proper engagement of local stakeholders and overall implementation of the action with and in these countries. On the modelling side, consortium partners have collaborated in the past with these partners, so basic research infrastructure is already shared. More importantly, on the training side, international arenas can be used (e.g., EMP-A, and the Joint Summer School on Modelling Tools for Sustainable Development), avoiding conflict territory. Such arenas feature both training and a high-level political forum, allowing consortium, local analysts, and stakeholders to meet and progress. If tensions further escalate, self-learning material can be shared with, and online assistance is offered to, key analysts from the local teams.

6 Conclusion

From February 2024 onwards, this updated version of the CDE plan will be the basic referential framework on which all communication and dissemination activities will be based on, while guiding the IAM COMPACT consortium towards drafting a strategy for the uptake of the project's exploitable outputs and findings, which will ensure scientific excellence and societal impact at the same time. The end goal is to present a clear vision of the ways and modes with which IAM COMPACT consortium plans for spreading its legacy and outcomes, moving progressively from fostering awareness of the project and topics associated, to eventually transforming them into actual impacts for the public good (e.g. improved policy delivery).

In terms of communication and dissemination, this CDE plan looks at ways to develop a strong and modern external communication mechanism, to be able to promote interdisciplinarity and science-policy and science-society dialogue in the production of integrated innovative high-end solutions to help decision-making and climate knowledge co-creation. In the light of such a two-way view, IAM COMPACT employs a wide range of activities from standard online and offline practices, such as the development of a website and communication through social media, newsletters distribution or thematic publications, both scientific and non-scientific, and conferences participation, to more dynamic ones, such as several joint co-production endeavours, whilst complying with the Open Science and FAIR data principles.

These include implementing synergies between EU-funded schemes and multi-scale networking with international modelling consortia or exploring the potential of making use of suggested tools and platforms used by other previous research projects, such as the I²AM PARIS platform, which has been developed under the H2020 PARIS REINFORCE and further expanded in H2020 NDC ASPECTS and in H2020 ENCLUDE. Most importantly, they dictate holding a number of capacity-building workshops in the four pilot countries to boost in-country interpretation of scientific evidence for practical action and guide the development of local model applications for national policy support, following along with the implementation of a series of co-creation modelling exercises under the Policy Response Mechanism operation. This represents one of the key novelties in IAM COMPACT, along with PRM, seeking to directly engage with a wide range of stakeholders from different disciplines and geographic scales at each step of the modelling process.

Results from these activities will be the backbone of the prospective exploitation strategy that IAM COMPACT will put on the table when moving to its third and final phase. As part of this mission, IAM COMPACT will draft consolidated policy recommendations to support the effective implementation of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and the development of 2030 decarbonisation strategies in respect of the Paris Agreement and its goals.

The success of the planned CDE effort will be regularly monitored through significant time-bound targets established at the onset of the project, to validate their accuracy and relevance to the IAM COMPACT's fundamental goals and envisaged outcomes. The final version of the present CDE plan thus will be provided in Month 36, together with a forward-looking approach to expand IAM COMPACT's exploitable results beyond its lifetime in a sustainable manner.

Annex 1. Networking and synergies

Table 23. Indicative list of relevant EU funded research projects

Project	Website	Partnership potential	Status	Contact partner
4C-CARBON	https://4c-carbon.eu/4c-project	Other relevancy	Ongoing	CICERO
AMPERE	https://ampere-euproject.eu/	Model enhancement for climate policy	Ongoing	
CAMPAIGNers	https://project.climate-campaigners.com/	Other relevancy	Ongoing	E3M, POLIMI
CDLinks	https://www.cd-links.org/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Closed	
Clima-Med	https://www.climamed.eu/	Other relevancy		NTUA
COMMIT	https://commitproject.eu/	Other relevancy	Closed	IMPERIAL, E3M
COP21 RIPPLES	https://cop21ripples.climatestrategies.org/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Closed	BRUEGEL
C-Track 50	https://www.c-track50.eu/	Other relevancy	Closed	NTUA
DIAMOND	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081179	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Open	E3M
DEEDS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776646	Other relevancy	Closed	E3M, KTH, UNIGE
ENCLUDE	https://encludeproject.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Ongoing	UPRC
ENGAGE	https://www.project-engage.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Ongoing	E3M, IIMA, THU
ENSYSTRA	https://ensystra.eu	Other relevancy	Closed	AAU
FULLFILL	https://fulfill-sufficiency.eu/	Other relevancy	Ongoing	POLIMI, WI
INNOPATHS	https://innopath.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Closed	E3M, Aalto
LOCOMOTION	https://www.locomotion-h2020.eu/	Model enhancement for climate policy	Ongoing	Uva, BC3, CARTIF
MAGICA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056920	Stakeholder dialogue/Capacity building	Ongoing	
MAIA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056935	Model enhancement for climate policy	Ongoing	BC3
N4C	https://www.nature4cities.eu/the-n4c-project	Other relevancy	Closed	CARTIF
NAVIGATE	https://www.navigate-h2020.eu/	Model enhancement for climate policy	Ongoing	E3M, UNIGE
NDC ASPECTS	https://ndc-aspects.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Ongoing	WI, BC3, E3M, IIMA, THU, UMD
NEVERMORE	https://www.nevermore-horizon.eu/	Stakeholder dialogue/Capacity building	Ongoing	Uva
openENTRANCE	https://openentrance.eu/	Energy transitions EMP-E	Ongoing	
OpTIMUS	https://www.optimus-smartcity.eu/	Stakeholder dialogue/Capacity building	Closed	KTH
PARIS REINFORCE	https://paris-reinforce.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Closed	NTUA, BC3, BRUEGEL, IMPERIAL, CICERO
PLAN4RES	https://www.plan4res.eu/	EMP-E Other relevancy	Closed	IMPERIAL
REEEM	https://www.reeem.org/	Energy transitions EMP-E	Closed	KTH, Aalto

Project	Website	Partnership potential	Status	Contact partner
REINVENT	https://www.reinvent-project.eu/	Other relevancy	Closed	WI
SENTINEL	https://sentinel.energy/	Energy transitions EMP-E	Ongoing	AAU, UPRC
SPINE	http://www.spine-model.org/index.htm	EMP-E Other relevancy	Closed	KTH
TIPPING+	https://tipping-plus.eu/home	Other relevancy	Ongoing	UPRC
WHY	https://www.why-h2020.eu/	EMP-E Other relevancy	Ongoing	E3M
WorldTrans	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081661	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Ongoing	

Table 24. Indicative list of relevant networks and consortia

Organisation	Website
ALLIANCES FOR CLIMATE ACTION	https://www.alliancesforclimateaction.org/
ALLIANCE FOR RURAL ELECTRIFICATION	https://www.ruralelec.org/
CARE-CLIMATE CHANGE & RESILIENCE INFORMATION CENTER	https://careclimatechange.org/
CCG-CLIMATE COMPATIBLE GROWTH	https://climatecompatiblegrowth.com/
CENII-EU GCC CLEAN ENERGY NETWORK II	https://www.ceps.eu/ceps-projects/eu-gcc-clean-energy-network-ii-cenii/
CEPS-CENTER OF EUROPEAN POLICY STUDIES	https://www.ceps.eu/
CLIMA-CENTER FOR CLIMATE RISK MANAGEMENT	https://www.clima.psu.edu/
CLIMATE ALLIANCE	https://www.climatealliance.org/home.html
CLIMATE REALITY	climaterealityproject.org
COMMUNITY ENERGY FOR ENERGY SOLIDARITY	https://www.energysolidarity.eu/
COP 21 RIPPLES	https://cop21ripples.climatestrategies.org/
EAPN-EUROPEAN ANTI-POVERTY NETWORK	https://www.eapn.eu/
EAUC-THE ALLIANCE FOR SUSTAINABILITY LEADERSHIP IN EDUCATION	https://www.eauc.org.uk/home
ECEMF-EUROPEAN CLIMATE & ENERGY MODELING FORUM	https://www.ecemf.eu/
EEG-ENERGY & ECONOMIC GROWTH Applied Research Program	https://www.energyeconomicgrowth.org/
ELARD-EUROPEAN LEADER ASSOCIATION FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT	http://elard.eu/
EMF-ENERGY MODELING FORUM	https://emf.stanford.edu/
EMP-E ENERGY MODELLING PLATFORM FOR EUROPE	https://www.energymodellingplatform.eu/
ENERGIZE Co2MMUNITY	https://co2mmunity.eu/
ENERGY CITIES	https://energy-cities.eu/
ENGAGER-ENERGY POVERTY ACTION: AGENDA Co-CREATION & KNOWLEDGE INNOVATION	https://www.engager-energy.net/
EPAH-ENERGY POVERTY ADVISORY HUB	https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/index_en
EURO CITIES	https://eurocities.eu/
EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION FOR INNOVATION IN LOCAL DEVELOPMENT	https://www.aeidl.eu/
EUROPEAN CLIMATE PACT	https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/european-green-deal/european-climate-pact_en
EUROPEAN RURAL DEVELOPMENT NETWORK	http://erdn.eu/

Organisation	Website
FREE INITIATIVE	https://www.rural-energy.eu/
GCCA-THE GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE ALLIANCE PLUS	https://www.gcca.eu/
	https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/gcca-community
GCP-GLOBAL CARBON PROJECT	https://www.globalcarbonproject.org/
HYDROGEN EUROPE	https://hydrogeneurope.eu/
IAMC-INTEGRATED ASSESMENT MODELING CONSORTIUM	https://www.iamconsortium.org/
IEA-WEO	-
IEPAW-INTERNATIONAL ENERGY POVERTY ACTION WEEK	https://www.energy-poverty-action.org/
IFLS-INSTITUTE FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH	https://www.ifls.de/en/
IPCC-INTERGOVERNMENTAL PANEL ON CLIMATE CHANGE	https://www.ipcc.ch/
OPENMOD-OPEN ENERGY MONDELLING INITIATIVE	https://openmod-initiative.org/
PCHES -PROGRAM ON COUPLED HUMAN & EARTH SYSTEMS	https://www.pches.psu.edu/
PIAMDDI-PROGRAM ON INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT MODEL DEVELOPMENT, DIAGNOSTICS & INTER-COMPARISON	https://www.pches.psu.edu/iamddi/
RedMENTES	https://redmentes.es/
RENOVATE EUROPE	https://www.renovate-europe.eu/
RIGHT TO ENERGY COALITION	https://righttoenergy.org/
RURAL ENERGY COMMUNITY ADVISORY HUB	https://rural-energy-community-hub.ec.europa.eu/index_en
STRN-SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITIONS RESEARCH NETWORK	https://transitionsnetwork.org/
UN CLIMATE CHANGE	unfccc.int
UN ENVIRONMENT PROGRAMME	unep.org
WCRP-WORLD CLIMATE RESEARCH PROGRAM	https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip/wgcm-cmip6

Table 25. Online collaboration platforms

Online collaboration platforms	Website link
Capacity4Dev	https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/
Climatechangemitigation.eu	http://climatechangemitigation.eu/
Climate-ADAPT	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/
IISD SDG Knowledge Hub	http://sdg.iisd.org/

Annex 2. Scientific and non-scientific events

Table 26. Indicative list of relevant scientific and non-scientific events

Event	Link	Level
4th European Conference Hydrogen & P2X 2023	https://fortesmedia.com/hydrogen-p2x-2023,4,en,2,1,22.html	EU
6th Annual World Congress of Smart Materials-2023	https://www.bitcongress.com/topwscsm2023/WelcomMessage.asp	International
7th Edition of Global Energy Meet	https://globalenergymeet.com/	International
AIAI 2023: 19th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	https://ifipaiai.org/2023/	EU
AIEE Energy Symposium	https://www.aieesymposium.eu/	EU
AIEE 4th International Conference	http://www.aiee.net/	International
ACEEE-Industry Summer Study	https://www.aceee.org/2023-industry-summer-study	International
Alliance to Save Energy EE Global	https://eeglobalalliance.org/ee-global-forum	International
BECC-Behavior, Energy & Climate Change Conference	https://becccconference.org/	International
Berliner Energietage	https://www.energietage.de/home.html	National
Berlin Green Investment Summit	https://wermutham.com/berlin-green-investment-summit-agenda/	National
C4E Forum	https://c4eforum.net/	International
CBA17-Conference on Community-Based Adaptation to Climate Change	https://www.globalresiliencpartnership.org/event/cba17-local-solutions-inspiring-global-action/	International
Cities Forum 2023-Together for green & just cities	https://www.uia-initiative.eu/en/events/cities-forum-2023-together-green-and-just-cities	EU
City Energy Conference 2023	https://eu-mayors.ec.europa.eu/en/node/538	EU
CO2 Capture & Reuse	https://fortesmedia.com/co2-capture-storage-reuse-2023,4,en,2,1,21.html	EU
CoEEE2023-International Joint Conference on Energy & Environmental Engineering	https://www.coeee.org/	International
Construmat-Building Sustainability	https://www.construmat.com/en/	EU
EasyChair Smart CFP (Archive)	https://easychair.org/cfp/	International
ECEEE -Summer Study	https://www.eceee.org/events/eceee-summer-studies/	EU
ECEMP-European Climate & Energy Modeling Platform Conferences	https://www.energymodellingplatform.eu/	EU
ECRES - European Conference on Renewable Energy Systems 2023	https://www.ecres.net/	EU
EREE 2023-5th International Conference on Environment, Resources & Energy Engineering	http://www.eree.org/	International
ESCC-International Conference on Energy, Sustainability & Climate Crisis	http://esc.uth.gr/	International
Ecomondo - The Green Technology Expo	https://www.ecomondo.com/	National

Event	Link	Level
Energy Modeling Forum (EMF) events	https://emf.stanford.edu/all-events	International
Energy Efficiency Finance Forum	https://www.aceee.org/2022-energy-efficiency-finance-forum	International
Energy and Sustainability 2023-10th International Conference	https://www.wessex.ac.uk/conferences/2023/energy-and-sustainability-2023	International
Energy Transition Summit 2023	https://marketforcelive.com/future-of-utilities/events/energy-transition-summit/?gclid=Cj0KCOAiJSeBhCCARIsAHnAzT8rU1Wqee58m-oXfQeuCu-ekUPqTizGRW8CFcGoCjXJH80juhvHumkaAmn7EALw_wcB	EU
EnergyTECH 2023: Renewable Energy, Resources and Sustainable Technologies	https://energytechconference.com/	International
ENLIT Europe	https://www.enlit-europe.com/	EU
EMC-Eastern Mediterranean Conference & Exhibition	https://emc-cyprus.com/#about	EU
EU Conference on modelling for policy support	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/event/2021-eu-conference-modelling-policy-support-collaborating-across-disciplines-tackle-key-en	EU
Eu-SPRI Annual Conference	https://www.euspri2023.com/	EU
EURO 33rd Conference	https://euro2024cph.dk/	EU
EURO events	https://www.euro-online.org/web/pages/100/conferences	EU
European Energy Transition Conference	https://www.climate-chance.org/en/event-calendar/2023-european-energy-transition-conference/	EU
European Hydrogen Week	http://www.euhydrogenweek.eu	EU
EUSEW-European Sustainable Energy Week	https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/	EU
EU-SPRI Annual Conference	https://www.euspri2023.com/	EU
ESEE (European Society for Ecological Economics) events	https://ecolecon.eu/category/events/upcoming-events/	EU
FLEXCON-Cocreate Flexible Energy	https://flexcon2022.eu/about/	International
FLINS/ISKE 2023	https://flins2022.scievent.com/	International
Forum on Scenarios for Climate and Societal Futures	https://scenariosforum.org/	EU
GEET-Green Energy & Environmental Technology International Conference	https://greenenergy-europe.eu/	International
Green Finance Research Advances Conference	https://green-finance-research-advances-2022.org/	EU
HAEE events	https://www.haee.gr/conferences-and-events/haee-events/	EU
IAMC Annual Meeting	https://www.iamconsortium.org/events/category/annual-meeting-of-the-iamc/	International
IAEE 44th International Conference	https://iaee2023.saudi-ae.sa/	International
IAEE 18th European Conference	https://www.iaee.org/en/conferences/europe.aspx	EU
ICEECC 2023: 17th International Conference on Energy, Environment & Climate Change	https://waset.org/energy-environment-and-climate-change-conference-in-march-2023-in-bangkok	International
ICEES 2023-7th International Conference on Energy and Environmental Science	http://www.icees.org/	International

Event	Link	Level
ICEESEN-International Conference on Energy, Environment & Storage of Energy	https://icesesen.com/	International
ICFEE 2023-13th International Conference on Future Environment and Energy	http://www.icfee.org/	International
IEPAW-International Energy Poverty Action Week	https://www.energy-poverty-action.org/	International
ICEEEP 2023: 7th International Conference on Energy Economics & Energy Policy	http://www.iceeep.com/	International
ICEDRD 2023: 17. International Conference on Environmental Design and Rural Development	https://waset.org/environmental-design-and-rural-development-conference-in-may-2023-in-rome	International
IISA 2023: 14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications	https://easyconferences.eu/iisa2023/	International
Island Finance Forum 2023: Investment for Sustainable Development	https://islandinnovation.co/events/island-finance-forum/?utm_source=sendinblue&utm_campaign=II136%20-%20Island%20Innovation%20Newsletter%2005012023&utm_medium=email	EU
Joint EASST/4S conference	https://www.4sonline.org/meeting/future-meetings/	International
Lisbon Energy Summit & Exhibition	https://www.lisbonenergysummit.com/?utm_source=google&utm_medium=cpc&utm_campaign=launch&gclid=Cj0KCCQiaIJSeBhCCARIsAHnAzT_rYwK9Dk8ffoCWnMgsDHT74B65PSN3IcbJv10Nt2WOIwdRkAaMO1QaAqaPEALw_wcB	International
REDay-Renovate Europe Day	https://www.renovate-europe.eu/	EU
RenewableEng-International Conference on Renewable & Sustainable Energy	https://xpertsmeetings.org/renewableeng23/	International
Right to Energy Forum 2023	https://righttoenergy.org/forum-2023/	EU
SCEW 2023: Smart City Expo World Congress	https://www.smartcityexpo.com/	International
SETAC Europe 33rd Annual Meeting	https://europe2023.setac.org/	EU
SEEP 2023- 15th International Conference on Sustainable Energy & Environmental Protection	https://seepconference.com/	International
SCORAI-ERCP WUR Conference: Transforming consumption-production systems towards just & sustainable futures	https://www.scp-conference-2023.com/web	EU
SCORAI-ERCP WUR Conference: Session " The Wellbeing Economy: Pathway to Consumption Sufficiency and a Post-Growth Economy?"	https://www.eceee.org/events/calendar/event/clone-abstracts-deadline-the-wellbeing-economy-pathway-to-consumption-sufficiency-and-a-post-growth-economy/	EU
SDEWES 18th Conference (Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems)	https://www.dubrovnik2023.sdewes.org/	EU

Event	Link	Level
SEED Conference-International Conference on the Sustainable Energy & Environmental Development	https://www.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/events/conferences/seeds-conference-2022/	International
Smart 2023: 10th ECCOMAS Thematic Conference on Smart Structures and Materials	https://www.smart2023.eu/	EU
Smart Cities Conferences 2023/2024/2025	https://conferenceindex.org/conferences/smart-cities	International
Smart Greens 2023: 12th International Conference on Smart Cities & Green ICT Systems	https://smartgreens.scitevents.org/	International
The JRC events/workshops	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/event/FutureEvents	International
The International Society for Ecological Modelling (ISEM) Global Conference 2023: Ecological Models for Tomorrow's Solutions	https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/international-society-for-ecological-modelling-global-conference?utm_campaign=STMJ_1666267551_CONF_NEWS_A&utm_medium=email&utm_source=Medlist&dqcid=STMJ_1666267551_CONF_NEWS_AB	International
UN climate change conference (COP28)	https://unfccc.int/	International
VIS 2023-Virtual Island Summit	https://islandinnovation.co/events/virtual-island-summit/	EU
WASET-World Academy of Science, Engineering & Technology (Archive)	https://waset.org/energy-conferences-in-2023	International
World Conference on Climate & Sustainability (Climate Week 2023)	https://climateweek.thepeopleevents.com/	International
World Green Building Week	https://worldgbc.org/	International
WSEC-World Smart City Expo	https://www.worldsmartcityexpo.com/fairDash.do?hl=ENG	International
WSED-World Sustainable Energy Days	https://www.wsed.at/	International

Annex 3. News and Media websites

Table 27. Indicative list of leading news and media channels

News and Media Channels	Website link
EC Website (CORDIS)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223239/factsheet/en
Research and Innovation Success Stories	https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/success-stories
EURACTIV	https://www.euractiv.com/
The Conversation	https://theconversation.com/
ClimateChangePost	https://www.climatechangepost.com/
The Guardian	https://www.theguardian.com/
Research*eu	https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/home_en.html
HORIZON magazine	https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine
The Beam	https://the-beam.com/